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North China Electric Power University

硕士学位论文

**智能快速开关型串联电容器在 25kV 辐射配
电网中的应用研究**

**Research on Application of An Intelligent and Fast
Switch Series Capacitor to 25kV Radial Power
Distribution Network**

Salah Mokred

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摘要

任何电力系统工作的目标都是为消费者提供足够的电力。这些系统不仅仅需要具有良好的可靠性，而且还需要满足较高的供电功率与电能质量。但是，如果在乡村及偏远地区使用较长的径向配电线来输送电能会面临诸多问题，第一个问题就是电压质量无法满足负载的需求，因为线路自身具有的电阻和电感是导致压降和功率损耗增加的两个主要重要因素。此外，同步电动机或鼠笼结构的电动机在进行启动操作时会消耗很高的无功功率，这个数值远远高于正常运行时的功率，同时在电动机启动期间所消耗的较高无功功率会造成供电端出现较大程度的电压降，对连接到供电网络的其他负载产生不利影响。严重情况下会导致电压降过大甚至无法启动电动机。所以相关研究者提出了若干补偿技术来解决这一难题，然而，针对在不同负载条件和功率因数下克服这一问题的独特解决方案的研究是一个热门研究课题。因此，本文发现串联电容器补偿具有改善电压质量的理想特性，而其他补偿技术则没有这些特性。此外，本文还对在不同负载条件和功率因数的情况下，串联和并联电容器补偿在径向配电网中应用的效果和特性进行了比较，评估和分析。

通过以上设计方案，在电动机启动过程中，固定的串联电容器组可为电动机提供足够的电压。第二个需要解决的问题是：在网络中插入固定串联电容器组时，应考虑启动操作期间异步/同步电动机中的次同步谐振问题。如果补偿程度过高，则该次同步谐振会更加危险。为了解决该问题，本文还提出了一种新的解决方案，以代替传统方法来避免次同步谐振问题。第三个问题是，当网络中发生故障时，串联电容器会承受非常大的过电压，并导致故障电流的级别快速增加。因此，本文介绍并设计了一种智能快速开关串联补偿装置，作为一种代替串联保护的新技术，以克服过压的严重性并减轻故障电流水平，从而代替了传统的保护方法。就电力设备的紧凑尺寸，高性能和较少的环境危害而言，这项新技术具有显著优势。此外，本文还对不同各种类型的故障（例如 Ph-g 单相对地，2Ph-g 两相对地和 3Ph-g 三相对地故障）条件下，新保护设备与常规保护设备的保护效果之间的效果进行了比较。针对以上所提到的所有研究内容，通过借助 MATLAB / SIMULINK 在电网系统正常和故障状况下设置不同负载条件和功率因数进行了仿真。在相关系统的设计中，一直以来迫切需要密闭性更好，更为稳定，高效且环保的设备。因此，本文所提出的快速开关串联补偿方案可有效减少金属氧化物压敏电阻的数量，从而降低了固定系列电容器组的成本与尺寸，并有效提升了工作效率。

关键词： 径向配电网，固定系列电容器组（FSCB），分流补偿（SHC），电压质量，金属氧化物压敏电阻（MOV）和火花隙，快速真空熔断器（FVCB）/旁路开关，快速开关串联补偿（FSSC），同步电动机，自励磁作用，次同步谐振（SSR）。

Abstract

The target of any electric power system is providing consumers with sufficient electrical power. They do not want reliability only but also demand high power quality. The delivery of electric power by long radial distribution line in the rural area faces up many problems. The first problem is that voltage quality cannot meet the requirements of a load because the line resistance and inductance are the two main significant factors causing an increase in voltage drop and power losses. Also, the synchronous motor or a squirrel cage induction motor consumed a high reactive power during starting operation, and the effect is even more extensive than that of consumed power during regular operation. The voltage drops during starting motor may be very high that it is not appropriate to the other clients connected to the network. In the worst case, the high reactive power consumed during motor starting causes the exaggerated voltage drops, thereby unable the motor to run. The investigators introduced some compensation techniques to solve this dilemma. However, the research of a unique solution to overcome this problem during different load conditions and power factor is a hot research topic. Therefore, this thesis discovered that the series capacitor compensation has ideal characteristics to improve voltage quality, and these characteristics are not available in other compensation techniques. Also, the thesis introduces the comparison, evaluation and analyzes of the effects and characteristics of series and shunt capacitor compensation application in the radial power distribution grid during different load conditions and power factors.

Furthermore, a fixed series capacitor bank supplies the motor with adequate voltage during starting. The second problem is that the subsynchronous resonance problem in asynchronous/synchronous motor during starting operation should be considered during inserted fixed series capacitor bank in the network. This sub-synchronous resonance is riskier if the degree of compensation is too high. However, to solve the problem, this thesis also suggests a new solution instead of conventional method to avoid the sub-synchronous resonance problem. The Third problem is that series capacitor exposes to the overvoltage severity and causes increasing in fault current level when the fault occurs in the network. Therefore, this thesis introduces an intelligent and fast switch series compensation device as a new technology for protection performance of series capacitor instead of the conventional protection method to overcome the overvoltage severity and mitigate the fault current level as well. This new technique has an advantage in terms of the compact size of power equipment, high performance and less environmental hazard. Also, the thesis presents a comparison between the results of the new protective device and

conventional protective equipment during various types of fault such as Ph-g, 2Ph-g, and 3Ph-g fault. Throughout the investigation mentioned above, simulation has been carried out with the help of MATLAB/SIMULINK during different load conditions and power factor in healthy and faulty conditions. Since a long time ago, there has been an utmost need for more airtight, cogent, coherent and environmentally robust equipment. Therefore, the fast switch series compensation reduces the number of MOV, which in turn, more economical, efficient and compact size of FSCB.

Keywords: Radial Power Distribution Network, Fixed Series Capacitor Bank (FSCB), Shunt Compensation (SHC), Voltage Quality, Metal Oxide Varistor (MOV) and Spark Gap, Fast Vacuum Circuit Breaker (FVCB)/Bypass Switch, Fast Switch Series Compensation (FSSC), Synchronous Motor, Self-excitation, Sub-synchronous resonance (SSR).

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Chapter 1 Introduction ,Background and Main Objectives

1.1 Introduction

The extended radial distribution network supplies the electric power to many consumers. Long distances separate customers all over the area. Therefore, many countries principally in the rural regions use a long radial power distribution line to provide the electric power for industrial and residential loads. The value of inductance increases when the power delivers by long transmission line causes increase in voltage drop and power losses. The use of series compensation in a radial distribution network has presented several benefits, and many projects confirm the technical and economic advantages over conventional methods of voltage control, which utilize automatic voltage regulators and shunt capacitors [1]. In the past few years, the STATCOM, SVC, and other compensation devices established power electronics technologies developed quickly. It failed to extend applications in the rural power distribution grid because of its high maintenance costs [2]. Currently, the FSCB technology in the high voltage transmission line has been extensively used at home and abroad [3],[4]. It also has a precise application in the low voltage distribution grid in Europe and the United State, but few apps in the domestic rural power distribution grid [5]. For an extended period, the series capacitors bank has been used to improve the system performances in transmission line. The sudden interruption of electric energy and the voltage drop are the most significant power quality disturbances in the electrical system. Also, the starting motor builds a high current with a low power factor causes a temporary voltage drop over the feeder [6],[7],[8]. The decline of voltage is unpredicted and ordinarily continues only little seconds while the motor attains a design speed [8]. It is a common problem that must be considered whenever the residential and industrial loads are supplied from the same feeder using a long distribution line [9]-[12].

FSCB has been identified as an economical solving to the lower voltage, power losses and voltage flicker problems. Additional FSCB in distribution grid decreases the reactance of the distribution grid. FSCB serves as voltage regulators that supply reinforcement in the voltage at the FSCB location. Moreover, this reinforcement in the voltage is continuous and instantaneous, which causes the notion of a natural option for quickly changing the loads that are existing [10]-[15]. However, when applying FSCB in the distribution grid, careful consideration requirement is inevitable to give series capacitor optimum location, Ferro-resonance phenomenon in the transformers, sub-synchronous resonance phenomenon (SSR), the value of ohmic

reactive, transient performance, short-circuit resistance, and the FSCB protection. The power distribution grid is a network system that directly supplies electric power to the consumer and its construction network. The lower voltage is a critical issue because the distribution network provides many distinct areas. It is not possible to keep up with the requirements of economic development when the grid structures are not strong enough; the equipment ageing, the negative supply will generate harmonics and other problems [15]-[18]. However, the quality of the power in the weak distribution network often cannot meet the requirements. The theoretical trajectory of line compensated using FSCB is outlined with the network conditions that should be stringency considered in applications. The thesis introduces a practical and simple method to select a good compensation degree.

Furthermore, the conventional method to protect the FSCB from the overvoltage severity is simulated and studied to compare the result with the new protective device in this thesis. The conventional protection method is combined with MOV and spark gap connected in parallel with FSCB [19]-[24]. However, in many practical applications where large number of MOV is required, it is not economical. In high fault current condition, it has to absorb a huge energy during faulty period and for this reason, MOV scheme functioned along with spark-gap scheme in order to bypass the FSCB when the energy reaches to the threshold level. For the aforementioned drawbacks, this thesis also presents the Fast Switch Series Compensation (FSSC) using Fast Vacuum Circuit Breaker (FVCB) as a new alternative technique solution having an ability to bypass the FSCB within 8ms and reinsert FSCB within 3ms as soon as the fault removed. Not only this, the new technique improves the system functionality during disturbance.

1.2 Research Background and Its Significance

The long radial distribution line supplies the electric power to many consumers. The customers are separated by long distances all over the area. Therefore, many countries principally in the rural regions use a long radial power distribution line to provide the electric power for industrial and residential loads. The value of inductance increases when the power delivers by long transmission line causes increase in voltage drop. Also, the rural power network was not attentive enough for a long time because of habitual causes, investment, and the rural power network at the end of the grid and other causes, so its structure and development are earnestly lagging related to the transmission power grid and civilized distribution grid. The construction of rural power distribution grid is relatively enervate, illogical distribution, equipment ageing and power supply radius are longer, especially agricultural network lines. Moreover, many power loads are distributed in different

regions, the distribution transformers are excessively distributing, and the naturalist power factor is low. All the factors mentioned above produce larger losses on the electric radial circuit causes decreasing the power quality. Furthermore, the voltage of the end line becomes lower because the voltage drops seriously affect the normal use of electric equipment users. The researchers present their efforts to solve the lower voltage problem at the end line of the rural power distribution network. They present some measures to solve this dilemma like using the distribution transformer tap to adjust the voltage, increasing the diameter wire and the PowerPoint and adopt the shunt capacitor reactive compensation [1]. The first technique is the easiest method to improve the voltage, but it has a limit regulation range. The second method has a high economic cost, and the replacement of the wires has little effects on reducing the low voltage brought by the line inductance, the third method is presently most used for progressing the power factor and minimizing the distribution line losses which has played an important effect. The typical switching shunt capacitor devices have a lower response; frequent switching operation cannot completely solve the voltage drop problem of the whole line and it is poorly compensated precision. When the system is overloading, the compensation of reactive power is lower, the voltage supporting impact is not evident, and the line voltages will increase when the line is light. At the same time, the parallel compensation devices in the power system mainly include electrostatic capacitors, SVC, SVG Etc., where SVC and SVG can dynamically adjust the compensation capacity as needed, but because of it's using in the distribution network not economical. The operating principles of parallel capacitors are also relatively simple, it is currently using more reactive compensation methods in the distribution network, but the actual compensation of the parallel capacitors, i.e. the capacity is proportional to the square of the voltage. When the system voltage is low, the effect of parallel compensation is reduced, so it cannot adapt well to the low voltage in the weak distribution network. SVC and SVG cost are relatively high, and their use in weak distribution networks is not economical, and it used less in distribution networks. FSCB is another type of compensation that uses controllable series compensation to increase the stability limit in the transmission network and line transmission capacity. The controllable series compensation reactance is variable, but its cost is high, and the operating principle is relatively complex. FSCB has different characteristics, and it has fixed reactance value, low cost, short construction period, and operation dimension simple protection features [25-28]. Therefore, the application of FSCB in various voltage levels of the distribution network is studied and analyzed. This thesis studies and analyses the essential

principles of the considerations for the applications of FSCB in the radial power distribution grid to improve the voltage and power quality.

1.3 Research Status at Home and Abroad

Both series capacitor compensation and shunt capacitor compensation are used to regulate the distribution network voltage, and they have two different mechanisms [29]-[30]. The shunt capacitor compensation provides reactive power to the connection point which is desired to compensate the load and its changes equivalent impedance of the load. The application of shunt capacitor banks presents many drawbacks: its application does not affect power factor or current beyond the point of its application, the reactive power provides by shunt capacitor compensation to compensate the load is instantly proportional to the bus voltages, the shunt capacitor is not sufficiently effective when the reactive power demand is lower, and the capacitor out will be high [29]. The application of FSCB is to minimize the voltage drop in the distribution lines and boost the voltage quality at the receiving end prominently when the power factor of loads is low. FSCB has been used since the early years of the 20th century. The application of FSCB dates returned to 1928 when the first FSCB on the New York power at the Ballston Spa Substation and were installed to 33 kV light grid by GE. The rated of FSCB was 1.2Mvar. Since then, all over the world installed the FSCB on power systems [30]. Sweden is the first country installed the FSCB for 245kV high voltage transmission line in 1951 [31]. Series capacitor bank was implemented firstly in Sweden for 400kV EHV transmission line in 1954[32]. The analogous project was achieved in the USA in 1951. The first 500 kV series capacitor compensation was introduced in the USA in 1960 [21]. Series capacitor compensation is widely used in high-voltage and ultra-high voltage transmission networks, railway power supply systems, and weak distribution networks [8], [32-36]. In the global power system, the total compensation capacity reached 100Gvar, covering 750/500/400/330/220kV voltage levels [34]. In China, the series capacitor compensation was first applied in 1954, mainly used in voltage levels below 35kV. In 1966, series capacitor compensation was used in 220kV lines. In 1972, it was applied in the 330kV line. At present, China has one 220kV line and more than ten 500kV lines equipped with series capacitor compensation, and the total capacity exceeds 10Gvar. From 1994-2005, Fortis Alberta in Canada has been installed seven units FSCB in different 25KV distribution feeders [7]. In 2005, the population of the Fortis Alberta reached to 3 million people and the surface area of 256,000 sq. miles (661,190 km²). In 2005, Fortis Alberta served 390,000 customers [7]. Load increase averages 4% per year in the service regions, i.e., the load increase averages 60% during 2005-2020 period. the

distribution feeders are radial and long. The average feeder length is 28 miles (45 km) and the longest feeder oncoming 62 miles (100 km). The FSCB installed in the line, which reduces the total inductance of the line and reduces the system electrical distance. This thesis proved that, the voltage effect of the series capacitor compensation increases with the increase of the load and decreases as the load decreases. Therefore, in the improvement of the voltage quality, the series compensation device of the same compensation capacity better than parallel compensation equipment. FSCB is fixed and cannot be changed, which is a convenient economical to operate the staff.

1.4 Research Status of FSCB Equipment

1.4.1 General Framework

FSCB exposes to the overvoltage severity that occurs in the system during faulty conditions. The investigators present their efforts to avoid this dilemma occurs. The investigators innovate many technologies to protect FSCB from overvoltage problem [9],[14],[38]-[41]. These technologies have been developed with the advancement of modern science. This thesis introduces new technology with excellent characteristics to avoid overvoltage problem (Chapter-4). Schemes for providing these protections are outlined in the following subsections below:

Fig. 1-1 Single line diagram of a FSCB protected through a self-sparking gap

- Description of Self-Sparking Gap Design

With this design, FSCB is provided by spark gap connected in parallel to avoid overvoltage problem as shown in fig. 1-1. The spacing between two carbon electrodes determines the level of spark over the gap is self-sparking. The gap

required is a tiny space between the main electrodes because of the minimum spark over required for the protection of economical distribution FSCB. The small space makes the gap spark-over exceedingly sensitive to external situations such as dirt, weather and insects. The gap is not self-extinguishing. the gap sparks over to avoid overvoltage problem across FSCB when the fault happens on the distribution grid. The current must be referred to a parallel circuit breaker/bypass switch as soon as spark occurs in the gap.

- Description of The Triggered Gap Design:

Fig. 1-2 illustrates the overvoltage protection equipment where the FSCB, metal oxide varistor (MOV), spark gap and bypass switch connected in parallel. The MOV is connected with a control system to set the spark gap trigger level. The MOV protects the FSCB dielectrics. More details in this scheme see chapter-4.

Fig. 1-2 Single line diagram of a FSCB protected through a triggered gap.

- Description of The Gapless Varistor Design

Fig. 1-3 illustrates the overvoltage protection equipment where the FSCB, metal oxide varistor (MOV), and bypass switch connected in parallel. The MOV units are not affected by external conditions such as weather, dirt or insects. The MOV absorbs the energy to protect FSCB until the breaker/bypass switch closes when the fault occurs in the power grid. In this design, the energy rating in MOV is higher than the energy rating in the triggered gap design. The MOV remains to conduct until the breaker/bypass switch closes or the power system circuit breakers cut off the fault. In little states where the FSCB has been utilized to increase fault currents, MOV protective level has been improved and the MOV designed to resist the full period of the fault and the bypass switch is delayed.

Fig. 1-3 Single line diagram of a gapless FSCB protected through a varistor.

1.4.2 Fixed Series Capacitor Bank (FSCB)

The compensation capacity of FSCB is not adjustable, so it is called a fixed series compensation device (FSC-Fixed Series Compensation). The compensation degree of fixed series capacitor compensation cannot be changed, and it is convenient economically to operate in the system. The main structure of FSCB contains many individual capacitor units are connected in series and parallel [19] & [39]-[43]. The X capacitors are connected in series, and the Y groups of capacitors are connected in parallel, as shown in Fig. 1-4. Either externally or internally fused units are utilized. It is normal to use a minimum of six units in parallel to each phase in the externally fused case to admit operation with a single blown fuse [14]. In both instances external or internal, the fuses should be considered able to operate when needed and when the current is as minimum as possible because the current of power frequency through capacitor elements or a failed capacitor is restricted by the current of the power system circuit, which may be very low.

Fig. 1-4 Series capacitor bank

The discharge current of the FSCB must withstand by the fuses from the protective standard voltage and system enjoined functions such as the fault current and the light load pickup. Manufacturers usually equip with these assortments.

1.5 Main Structure for FSCB Protection

To protect FSCB from the overvoltage severity and mitigate fault current magnitude, the FSCB contains the following structures:

1. MOV
2. Control System
3. Damping Circuit
4. Spark Gap
5. Circuit Breaker/Bypass Switch

More explain for these structures see Chapter-4

1.6 Thyristor Controlled Series Capacitors (TCSC)

The TCSC is basically a series-connected Static Var Compensation (SVC) system. The main construction of TCSC design was first suggested in 1986 by an investigators team lead by J.J. Vithayathil as a means of “rapid adjustment of network impedance (RANI)”, which boosted transient stability and a controlled loop flow [44-45]. A device consisting of thyristor, reactor, and protection control device connected to both ends of the series capacitor compensation is called Thyristor Control Series Compensation (TCSC) [46-47].

Fig. 1-5 Series capacitor bank Structures (a) TSSC structures (b) TCSC structures

There are two types of adjustable series capacitor compensation: thyristor switched series capacitor (TSSC) and thyristor-controlled series capacitors (TCSC) [47-48].

The TSSC structure is shown in Fig. 1-5a; the TCSC structure is shown in Figure 1-5b. References [49] and [50] offered comprehensive information on the TCSC design.

1.7 Research Status of FSCB for Improving Voltage Quality of Distribution Network

In the distribution network, voltage quality is an essential issue in power supply quality [19]. The demand for various power consumers for good power quality is gradually increasing, and the requirements of power supply departments for power supply quality are getting higher and higher. Due to the relatively backward construction of the distribution network, there are problems such as prolonged power supply lines, outdated equipment, and inadequate management. Many distribution networks, coupled with the increase of various power equipment and industrial load have the situation of insufficient reactive power, excessive loss, and long-term failure of voltage quality [49, 50]. Among the solutions for various problems in the distribution network, reactive power compensation and voltage regulation are two significant aspects. For long lines, series capacitor compensation can improve the network parameters of the power supply line by compensating the reactive power and regulates the voltage of the grid to boost the network with an excellent adjustment effect [51]. In foreign countries, to solve the voltage problem in the distribution grid, the application of FSCB is widely used, for example, in China, Canada, United States, and other countries. Series capacitor compensation has a history of more than 80 years [8] and there are many studies. However, there are few applications of this technology in the distribution network. The reference [52] is a monograph on power system series compensation. The basic theory of compensation application focuses on the effects of series capacitor compensation on stability, relay protection and sub-synchronous resonance (SSR) phenomenon, test maintenance and series capacitor design of series capacitors [53],[8]. The reference [54] explains the influence principle of series capacitor compensation on relay protection, and mainly focuses on the analysis of the effect of series compensation on transmission lines. The series capacitor compensation technology is rarely used in domestic distribution networks, and there are few related kinds of literature, especially the application analysis of fixed series capacitor compensation in multiple distribution network voltage levels. Therefore, it is essential to analyze the compensation capacity and selecting the appropriate location of the series capacitor compensation.

1.8 Contents

In this research, many problems have been solved during deliver electric power by long radial distribution line during steady state and disturbance condition. The voltage and power quality problems are the main problems in the radial distribution line. Inserted fast switch series capacitor device in a radial distribution network presents many technical and economic improvements during steady state and disturbance as well. All the problems cited above have been solved and achieved by the following research contents of this paper:

Chapter-1: It explained problem introduction, background behind conducting this research, the leading causes of voltage and power quality problem, introduced the previous studies and comparable between the new technique in this paper and the past technologies and research benefits discussed.

Chapter-2: It proved the role of the series capacitor in improving voltage and power quality in a radial distribution network by basic theoretical theory and phasor diagrams. Also, it presents designs to select the optimum location of series capacitor bank according to the load condition.

Chapter-3: It explained the Comparison of the Effect of Series and Shunt Capacitor Application in 25kV Radial Power Distribution Network. The investigators introduced some compensation techniques to solve the voltage drop problem. However, the research of a unique solution to overcome this problem is a hot research topic. Therefore, this paper discovered that the series capacitor compensation has ideal characteristics to improve voltage quality, and these characteristics are not available in other compensation techniques. Also, the paper introduces the comparison, evaluation and analyzes of the effects and characteristics of series and shunt compensation application in the radial distribution grid during different load conditions and power factors.

Chapter-4: It explained the comparative evaluation results and analysis of protection performance of series capacitor between the conventional method and the new technology method (fast switch series compensation device) during various type of faulty condition.

Chapter-5: Consideration the application of FSCB during self-excitation motor which causes sub-synchronous resonance phenomenon and introduces a new technique instead of conventional method to avoid this problem.

Chapter-6: In this chapter, we will draw a comprehensive conclusion of the above-proposed system with reasonable and unique solutions to boost the voltage and power quality; avoiding overvoltage severity across the FSCB and suppressing the SSR phenomenon when the motor start to operate.

Chapter 2 Basic Principles, Advantages and Impact of the Application of FSCB To Radial Power Distribution Networks

2.1 Introduction

Insertion of a series capacitor bank to a radial distribution network minimizes the reactance of that network which leads to improving the voltage quality along the line. With the quick economy development, the require for high power quality is getting higher and higher. However, at present there are still low voltage dilemmas in radial power distribution network, which cannot meet the requirements of loads. Aiming at the drawbacks of the existing voltage regulation mode, the utilize of series capacitor bank technology in radial distribution network with low voltage problems is suggested. Installing FSCB to a radial power distribution line decreases the reactance of that line. For the natural condition of lagging power factor loads, installing the FSCB reduces the voltage drop associated with the load current for all loads on the line downstream from the FSCB. As will be offered, the series capacitor works as a voltage regulator that supplies a reinforce in voltage at the location of capacitor that is proportional to the magnitude of circuit current and the sine of the power factor angle. Moreover, this reinforces in voltage is instantaneous and continuous as well, which makes the connotation a natural option where rapidly variable loads are existing. Thus, ideal use for FSCB on radial distribution network is to minimize voltage variations on this network caused by large changing inductive loads, this is principally different from shunt capacitor response, which cannot be smoothly responsive to rapid load.

2.2 Voltage and Power Conditions in a Radial Circuit Without/With Series Capacitor Bank

The leading theory of voltage and power condition and their phasor diagram are briefly explained in the following subsections:

2.2.1 Voltage and Power Conditions Without Series Capacitor Bank

The fundamental theory of series capacitors bank application can be illustrated with the circuit in fig. 2-1 which outlined a simple model consisting of resistance and inductive reactance connected in series as a typical radial circuit

Fig. 2-1 (a) A Sample Radial Circuit Model Without Compensation (b) Phasor Diagram

As shown in the simple system of Fig.2-1, the real and reactive power transmitted in this system are:

$$P_r = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_T} \sin \delta \quad (2-1)$$

$$Q_r = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_T} (1 - \cos \delta) \quad (2-2)$$

Where:

$$X_T = X_{sr} + X_{trs} + \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} X_{Li} \quad (2-3)$$

X_{sr} is the inductive impedance of source,

X_{trs} is the inductive impedance of transformer,

$\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} X_{Li}$: represents the total inductive reactance along radial distribution circuit

Equations (2-1) and (2-2) illustrates that the real and reactive power in the radial circuit directly proportional with the inductive reactance i.e. the transmission capacity of real and reactive power is lower when the inductive reactance value is very high and vice versa. For three phase networks, the inductive reactance is the positive sequence reactance of the circuit. The loads with the power factor $\cos \varphi_r$ feeds by the radial circuits. In each phase, the voltage drop from the source to the loads is illustrated as:

$$\Delta V = V_{se} - V_{re} \cong R_{Li} I_{Li} \cos \varphi_r + X_T I_{Li} \sin \varphi_r \quad (2-4)$$

The delivered active power and reactive power terms can be expressed by the approximation (2-4). The active power and the reactive power absorb by the loads can also be expressed as

$$P_r = V_{re} I_{Li} \cos \varphi_r \quad (2-5)$$

$$Q_r = V_{re} I_{Li} \sin \varphi_r \quad (2-6)$$

The expressions (2-5) and (2-6) can be utilized in expression (2-4) to express the voltage drop as:

$$\Delta V \cong \frac{P_r R_{Li} + Q_r X_T}{V_{re}} \quad (2-7)$$

There are three different load cases depending on nature of loads can be distinguished:

- Resistive loads such as electric heating, incandescent lighting and power factor corrected load
- Inductive loads such as normal household, industrial and mercantile loads
- Capacitive Loads such as variable or fixed capacitor banks, shunt capacitor and unloaded cable network

Fig. 2-2 Phasor diagrams with loads of different power factors. The load power factor = $\cos \theta_r$.
 (a) Resistive load (b) Inductive load (c) Capacitive load

Fig. 2-2 depicted the phasor diagrams for these various cases. This figure can be illustrating the following conclusions. A resistive load or an inductive load causes a voltage reducing at the loads, whereas a capacitive load inclined to cause a voltage growth at the loads. The voltage growth magnitude minimized by the distribution circuit resistance.

2.2.2 Voltage and Power Conditions with Various Compensation Degree of Series Capacitor Bank

Now consider the radial circuit in fig. 2-3, which illustrates a typical series capacitor compensated radial circuit.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2-3 (a) Single line diagram of a series compensated radial circuit with load. (b) Phasor diagram for inductive load. power factor of load = $\cos \varphi_r$, (c) Phasor diagram for resistive load.

The load power factor = $\cos \varphi_r$

In this circuit, the inductive expressing X_T in (2-1), (2-2), (2-4) and (2-7) can be substituted by the equivalent reactance X_{new} , where:

$$X_{new} = X_T - X_C \quad (2-8)$$

X_C represents the reactance of series capacitor bank. The active power (P_r), reactive power (Q_r) and the voltage drop (ΔV) can be represented in the following equations:

$$P_r = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_{new}} \sin \delta = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_T - X_C} \sin \delta \quad (2-9)$$

$$Q_r = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_{new}} (1 - \cos \delta) = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_T - X_C} (1 - \cos \delta) \quad (2-10)$$

$$\Delta V \cong R_{Li} I_{Li} \cos \varphi_r + X_{new} I_{Li} \sin \varphi_r = R_{Li} I_{Li} \cos \varphi_r + (X_T - X_C) I_{Li} \sin \varphi_r \quad (2-11)$$

$$\Delta V \cong \frac{P_r R_{Li} + Q_r X_{new}}{V_{re}} = \frac{P_r R_{Li} + Q_r (X_T - X_C)}{V_{re}} \quad (2-12)$$

Here, the series compensation degree of the line defined as γ :

$$\gamma = \frac{X_C}{X_T} \quad 0 \leq \gamma \leq \gamma_{\max} \quad (2-13)$$

FSCB is inserted to the grid to achieve the best voltage profile along the radial circuit. X_{new} is defined as the equivalent total inductive reactance from the source to the end line which feeds the furthest load. The equivalent inductance term X_T in (2-7) -(2-12) can be substituted by equation (2-13) to obtain the following equations:

$$X_{new} = X_T (1 - \gamma) \quad (2-14)$$

$$P_r = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_{new}} \sin \delta = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_T (1 - \gamma)} \sin \delta \quad (2-15)$$

$$Q_r = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_{new}} (1 - \cos \delta) = \frac{V_{se} V_{re}}{X_T (1 - \gamma)} (1 - \cos \delta) \quad (2-16)$$

$$\Delta V \cong R_{Li} I_{Li} \cos \varphi_r + X_{new} I_{Li} \sin \varphi_r = R_{Li} I_{Li} \cos \varphi_r + X_T (1 - \gamma) I_{Li} \sin \varphi_r \quad (2-17)$$

$$\Delta V \cong \frac{P_r R_{Li} + Q_r X_{new}}{V_{re}} = \frac{P_r R_{Li} + Q_r X_T (1 - \gamma)}{V_{re}} \quad (2-18)$$

In the case the degree of compensation is $\gamma = 50\%$, from equations (2-15) and (2-16) the active power and reactive power double i.e. the delivered active power and reactive power increase when the degree of compensation increases and vice versa. Moreover, from equations (2-17) and (2-18), it is noticed that the voltage reduction decreases when the degree of compensation increases and vice versa. When the series compensation changed, the power curve on the line is shown in Fig. 2-4. Through the critical point of voltage stability with different compensation degrees, the series compensation can effectively improve the transmission power and voltage stability of the line.

Fig. 2-4 Voltage-Power Curve with Different Compensation Degree

In the distribution network, fixed series capacitor compensation is used in the distribution network, mainly to compensate the reactive power and regulate the voltage.

The terminal voltage boosted by the series capacitor is:

$$\Delta V' = \Delta V - \Delta V_c = \frac{QX_c}{V_{se}} = \frac{\gamma QX_T}{V_{se}} \quad (2-19)$$

Define the compensation efficiency of the series capacitor as η :

$$\eta = f(\gamma) = \frac{\partial(\Delta V')}{\partial \gamma} = \frac{QX_T}{V_{se}} \quad (2-20)$$

Fig. 2-5 Curve of The Relation Between (a) The Compensation Degree and Voltage (b) Compensation Degree and Compensation Efficiency

The reactive power Q in the power line is a function of the compensation degree γ . As the compensation degree increases, the series capacitor compensates for a part of the inductive reactive power, and Q becomes smaller, so $f(\gamma)$ is a decreasing function of γ . As shown in Fig. 2-5, it is noticed that the voltage boosted by the unit compensation capacity will gradually increase when the degree of compensation gradually increases and the compensation efficiency will decrease. [55]

Fig. 2-6 The Phasor Diagrams With Different Power Factors (a) The Degree Of Compensation $\gamma < 1$ (b) The Degree Of Compensation $\gamma = 1$ (c) The Degree Of Compensation $\gamma > 1$

Depending upon equations (2-13) -(2-14), three different states can be determined:

- 1- The total equivalent X_{new} of compensated circuit is inductive when the degree of compensation $\gamma < 1$, i.e. $X_T > X_C$ and this condition can be called Under Compensated (UC)
- 2- The total equivalent X_{new} of compensated circuit is zero when the degree of compensation $\gamma = 1$, i.e. $X_T = X_C$ and this condition can be called Full Compensated (FC).
- 3- The total equivalent X_{new} of compensated circuit is capacitive when the degree of compensation $\gamma > 1$, i.e. $X_T < X_C$ and this condition can be called Over Compensated (OC)

The phasor diagrams in fig. 2-6 illustrate the three aforementioned different conditions.

In FSCB, the rated current of each capacitor is I_{LC} , the rated voltage is V_{LC} , and the rated capacity is $Q_C = V_{LC} I_{LC}$, then the maximum load current I_{Cmax} can be successfully passed. When the required capacitive reactance value is X_C , calculate the number of capacitors connected in series X and the number of parallel capacitor Y (fig. 1-4). Finally, calculate the total capacity Q_C of the three-line capacitors. The total number of capacitors required for three lines is 3XY [56].

$$\begin{cases} YI_{LC} \geq I_{Cmax} \\ XV_{LC} \geq I_{Cmax} \\ Q_C = 3XYQ_{LC} = 3XYV_{LC}I_{LC} \end{cases} \quad (2-21)$$

The voltage level of one line is V, the impedance of the whole line is $R_{Li} + jX_{Li}$, the power delivered is $P_r + jQ_r$, the voltage at the first end is V_{re1} , and the end voltage is not less than V_{re2} . The single point series capacitor compensation is applied to the line, and the method of estimating the series capacitor compensation capacity is as follows:

The voltage drop before compensation is:

$$\Delta V = \frac{P_r R_{Li} + Q_r X_{Li}}{V_{re1}} \quad (2-22)$$

The voltage drop allowed after compensation is:

$$\Delta V = V_{re1} - V_{re2} \quad (2-23)$$

The capacitive reactance required for compensation is:

$$X_C = \frac{V(\Delta V - \Delta V_C)}{Q_r} \quad (2-24)$$

The maximum current through the line is:

$$I_{\max} = \frac{\sqrt{P_r^2 + Q_r^2}}{\sqrt{3} \times V} \times 1000 \quad (2-25)$$

The capacitors in the capacitor bank are usually capacitors of the same type and have the same parameters, such as oil-immersed capacitors with rated voltage $V_{LC} = 0.6KV$, capacity $Q_{LC} = 20KVAR$, $I_{LC} = 33.33A$, $X_{LC} = 18\Omega$

Calculate the number of capacitors that need to be connected in parallel Y:

$$Y \geq \frac{I_{\max}}{I_{LC}} \quad (2-26)$$

The number of capacitors that need to be connected in series X:

$$X \geq \frac{I_{\max} X_c}{V_{LC}} \quad (2-27)$$

The actual compensation capacitance and compensation are:

$$X_C = \frac{XX_{LC}}{Y} \quad (2-28)$$

$$Q_C = 3XYQ_{LC} = 3XYV_{LC}I_{LC} \quad (2-29)$$

When there are various loads along the line or the system construction is more complicated, if the single-point series capacitor compensation cannot meet the requirements of improving the voltage quality, a series capacitor compensation can be added on this basis to form a two-point series capacitor compensation [56].

2.3 Some Relations for The Circuit Voltage Calculations

Fig. 2-7 explains the effect of series capacitor bank on the circuit voltage and can be calculated as the following relations:

Fig. 2-7 The apparent active and reactive power, and the voltages on both sides of a series capacitor bank in any qualitative circuit. Single line quantities.

$$S_{re} = V_{re} I \quad (2-30)$$

$$S_{se} = V_{se} I \quad (2-31)$$

Where:

$$\frac{V_{re}}{V_{se}} = \frac{S_{re}}{S_{se}} = \frac{\sqrt{P_{re}^2 + Q_{re}^2}}{\sqrt{P_{re}^2 + (Q_{re} - Q_C)^2}} \quad (2-32)$$

Where Q_C represents the series compensation reactive power according to (2-38).

According to (2-32) the maximum voltage increase (φ_r lagging) is acquired

for $Q_C = Q_r$, which gives:

$$\left(\frac{V_{re}}{V_{se}} \right)_{\max} = \frac{S_{re}}{P_{re}} = \frac{1}{\cos \varphi_r} \quad (2-33)$$

Notice that (2-33) presents a theoretic maximum. In a functional condition, various obstructions, such as limitation on overcompensations, series capacitor bank location on the circuit, etc. have to be take into account.

Fig. 2-8 Phasor diagram for the line to ground voltage on each side of a series capacitor bank in a qualitative circuit. Single line quantities.

Fig. 2-8 is obtained the following approximate expressing:

$$V_{re} - V_{se} \cong I_{Li} X_C \sin \varphi_r \quad (2-34)$$

Or line to line value:

$$\Delta V_{L-L} \cong \sqrt{3} I_{Li} X_C \sin \varphi_r \quad (2-35)$$

2.4 Reactive Power of Series Capacitor Bank

In each phase of a series capacitor bank, the following equations are righteous for voltage, current and reactive power. Reference is indicated to fig. 2-3a.

$$\overline{V}_C = -jX_C \overline{I}_C \quad (2-36)$$

$$\overline{S}_C = P_C + jQ_C = \overline{V}_C \overline{I}_C^* = -jX_C |I_C|^2 \quad (2-37)$$

$$Q_C = -X_C |I_C|^2 \quad (2-38)$$

Where the current I_C^* is the conjugate of current I_C

The three-line reactive power is:

$$Q_{C-3ph} = 3Q_C \quad (2-39)$$

The expressing in equation (2-37) shows that the FSCB delivered the reactive power to the circuit where is the reactive power sign is negative. Moreover, notice that the reactive power Q_C proportional to X_C and I_C^2 .

2.5 Voltage Profile on a Compensated Radial Circuit

The voltage profile on a radial circuit is the voltage magnitude in the face of distance from the source end of the radial circuit. This voltage profile relies on the parameters of the radial circuit, the load magnitude and the power factor of the loads, as mentioned previously. It will vary from time to time;(i.e. from hour to hour) as the steady-state loads fluctuate and may vary from second to second as loads are substituted, and motors are started. The maximum load with the maximum inductive current is usually the one of most significant interest, because it represents the maximum voltage variation from the source to the end of the circuit, and may happen when the source voltage is low. A representative voltage profile for a radial circuit in various load conditions;(i.e. No-load condition and maximum load condition) with and without series capacitor bank is shown in fig. 2-9. The currents due to the circuit capacitance as well as the exciting current of transformers are negligent. We Observed that the curve of voltage profile has an abruption or hop at the location of FSCB. There is a substantial increase voltage on the circuit downstream from the FSCB. Also, observe that the increased voltage on the circuit downstream from the FSCB minimizes the current towed by the motor loads situated there lead up to a small increase in voltage upstream from the FSCB. Observe that the voltage drops in the cases of a large motor starting, the voltage will be slightly lower on the source side of the FSCB because the FSCB is increasing the voltage at the motor, which raises motor starting current (See Ch-5).

2.6 Effect of FSCB in Fault Current

At first glance, it appears credible to decide that the series capacitor bank in a radial circuit rises the fault current level because of the capacitive reactance null or reduce the reactance from the source to the position of fault [8]. However, this is only partly true. The reasons are that the investigators present many technics to limits the fault current and overvoltage protection. This research introduces a new technology to avoid this dilemma (Chapter-4). The investigators suggested that the FSCB should always be provided by bypass switch which will immediately bypass the FSCB in a stat of a high current line fault downstream from the FSCB.

2.7 Selecting the Location of FSCB

The choice of the FSCB location is usually based on the effect of compensation and the actual network conditions. Different systems should follow different site selection principles [8],[19], [34]. Series capacitor installation methods mainly include:

1. A single set of FSCB is located at the beginning, center and end of the line;
2. In some conditions, two sets of FSCB are situated on the line, such as the first and last segments of the line or at 1/3 and 2/3 of the radial distribution line.

For the radial distribution network, the installation location can be selected as follows:

- 1) The system voltage distribution is uniform and meets the requirements.
- 2) When the load is concentrated at the end (Fig. 2-9a), the series compensation device should be installed at the end of the system because this location reduces the exposure of FSCB to stresses due to various types of fault to achieve a more economical designing of the FSCB.
- 3) When the load is distributed along the line, FSCB is installed where the voltage drop is 1/3 to 1/2 of the entire voltage drops of the circuit. The system voltage for different situations is shown in Fig. 2-9b.

In engineering practices, the determination of the FSCB location is not depends only on the distribution of load and power in the system, but also on the topographical characteristics of the power transmission corridor and the ease of operation and maintenance after installation.

Fig. 2-9 The Optimum FSCB Location in the case (a) The load is concentrated at the end of the line (b) There are several loads along the line

2.8 Summary

This chapter mainly introduces the basic principle and theoretical theories of series capacitor compensation used in the distribution network and analyzes its effect on the improvement of transmission capacity and the voltage of the distribution network. In this chapter, the paper proves by the underlying theory and the phasor diagrams the effect of inserted of FSCB to the radial network. The following significant conclusions about the task of FSCB in a radial circuit can be made:

1. The FSCB provides the system with an essential rise in the voltage at the load and makes the consumer receive the power with a high quality even the loads have a high inductive value, (i.e. the effect of FSCB is more effective due to a lower value of the power factor of the load).
2. The voltage rise supplied at the load by FSCB is little when the power factor of the load equal to 1.0, i.e. when the load is resistive. The sending end voltage is greater than the receiving end voltage. This phenomenon is also true when the compensation degree is more than 100%.
3. If the load downstream from the FSCB is capacitive or has a major capacitive component then the FSCB provides a voltage reduction at the load
4. Any change on the series compensation degree led to change the voltage regulation value as the compensation degree increases, the voltage regulation efficiency decreases, so the appropriate compensation degree should be selected.

Chapter 3 Comparison of the Effect of Series and Shunt Capacitor Application in 25KV Radial Power Distribution Network

3.1 Introduction

The line resistance and inductance are the main two major parts causes increase the voltage drop. Usually, the reactance of wire is much higher than the line resistance due to using a big section of wire in long lines. Deliver the electric power system by long distribution line causes increase in voltage drop in the distribution lines. The radial distribution network with long 60Km has some problems such as a huge voltage drop and high-power losses in the distribution lines because the long distance and the high reactance value. However, the investigators introduced some compensation techniques. Therefore, the research of a unique solution to solve this dilemma is a hot research topic. Therefore, this thesis discovered that the series capacitor compensation has ideal characteristics to improve voltage quality, and these characteristics are not available in other compensation techniques. Also, the thesis introduces the comparison, evaluation and analyzes of the effects and characteristics of series and shunt capacitor compensation application in the radial power distribution grid during different load conditions and power factors. The reactive power is insufficient due to heavy load in some weak distribution grid and the voltage quality cannot meet the requirements of load, i.e. when the voltage less than 7% of the standard voltage. In distribution grid, Shunt and series capacitor can play a role in improving voltage quality but the principle and influence of compensation are different.

3.2 Comparison, Principles and Effects of Application of Series and Shunt Compensation to Radial Distribution Network

3.2.1 Analysis and Principle

In the simple power distribution system shown in Figure 3-1a, there is a series capacitor compensation and parallel compensation device. The phasor diagram in figure 3-2b illustrates the voltage drop in the system when there is no series or shunt compensated adopted in the circuit. The phasor diagram in figure 3-2c illustrates the voltage drop in the system when there is only series compensated installed in the circuit. The phasor diagram in figure 3-2d shows the voltage drop in the system

when there is only shunt compensated installed in the circuit. It can be seen that the series capacitor compensation and the shunt compensation can reduce voltage drop, but the compensation influence of series capacitor compensation is more evident.

Fig. 3-1 (a) Series and Parallel Capacitor Compensation, (b) Voltage drop when there is no series or shunt capacitor compensation, (c) Voltage drop during series capacitor compensation, (d) Voltage drop during shunt capacitor compensation

When there is no series or shunt compensated in radial circuit, the voltage drop value at the end line is:

$$\Delta V \cong \frac{P_r R_{Li} + Q_r X_{Li}}{V_{re}} \quad (3-1)$$

X_{Li} is the reactance value in distribution line. It is clear from equation (3-1) the voltage drop can be reduced due to decrease the reactance value. The voltage drops in equation (3-1) change to the equation (3-2) due to inserted FSCB in radial circuit to improve voltage quality by minimizing the inductive reactance in distribution line.

$$\Delta V = \frac{P_r R_{Li} + Q_r (X_{Li} - X_c)}{V_{re}} = \frac{P_r R_{Li} + Q_r X_{Li}}{V_{re}} - \frac{Q_r X_c}{V_{re}} \quad (3-2)$$

From equation (3-1), it also illustrates that the voltage drop increases due to increase the reactive inductive load when the load is large (low power factor). In

this case, the voltage in the extreme load is very low. Therefore, the FSCB is adopted in the system to solve aforementioned problem in equation (3-1) and the voltage drop decreases which is shown in equation (3-2) the larger voltage part

$\frac{Q_r X_C}{V_{re}}$ compensated by FSCB.

On the contrary, when the system load is reduced, the voltage partially compensated by the series capacitor is reduced. Therefore, series capacitor compensation has a good self-regulating effect. When shunt capacitance compensation installed to the system at the load node, the voltage drop at the end of the line is:

$$\Delta V = \frac{PR + X_{Li}(Q - Q_C)}{V_{re}} = \frac{PR + X_{Li}Q}{V_{re}} - \frac{X_{Li}Q_C}{V_{re}} \quad (3-3)$$

However, the reactance value of the shunt capacitor compensation device in the distribution network is fixed, and the actual compensation capacity is determined by the voltage, namely:

$$Q_C = \frac{V_{re}^2}{\bar{X}_c} \quad (3-4)$$

Where \bar{X}_c represents the reactance value of the shunt capacitor then:

$$\Delta V = \frac{PR + X_{Li}Q}{V_{re}} - \frac{V_{re} X_{Li}}{\bar{X}_c} \quad (3-5)$$

The voltage portion $\frac{V_{re} X_{Li}}{\bar{X}_c}$ compensated by the shunt capacitor is smaller when

the load is high. The larger voltage portion $\frac{V_{re} X_{Li}}{\bar{X}_c}$ compensated by the shunt

capacitor during light load condition. This is exactly opposite of the required adjustment direction. The lower voltage happened in the system due to the heavier the load and it is the worse compensation effect of the parallel reactive power compensation device.

3.2.2 Voltage Deviations Standard

Delivering the electric power through long radial distribution line creates a great influence on the system voltage and power parameters, and there is often insufficient load reactive power compensation in the distribution network. Excessive load causes voltages to be low, and load fluctuations cause voltage fluctuations and other problems. Voltage quality in distribution network system related to the reactive power. When the reactive power cannot be balanced locally,

the reactive power must pass through the distribution line. For the load power factor in the system, refer to Canadian technical guidelines: 25kV and above, etc. For load conditions, the power factor should not be lower than 0.9; for some loads, it should be greater than 0.85. Voltage deviation is the relative difference value of the deviation of the voltage of the power system from the nominal voltage during operation and the system standard voltage value, expressed as a percentage:

$$V_d \% = \frac{V_{st} - V_{me}}{V_{st}} \times 100\% \quad (3-6)$$

Where the V_d is the voltage deviation, V_{me} is the voltage measurement and V_{st} is the voltage standard value.

Table 3-1 Voltage Deviation Standard.

References [58],[59]: At Service Entrance per CSACAN3-C235-83	
Voltage Level	Voltage Deviation
25kV and bellow	±7%
120-240 V single phase	+5.83%, -11.67%
Specially requested users	Determined by both parties

In each voltage level, the limits are shown in Table 3-1. In the operation of the power sector, the voltage deviation of 25kV is usually ±7% (23.25 kV-26.75kV). In China in the operation of the power sector, the voltage deviation of 35kV is usually ±5% (33.25kV-36.75kV) and the 10kV voltage deviation is typically ±7% (9.3kV-10.7kV) [25]-[26], [58].

3.3 Investigation of The Voltage Quality Without/With FSCB

3.3.1 Model Characteristics

The voltage profile in the electric radial circuit depends on the parameters of the radial line, the load power factor, and the magnitude of load. When steady state load changes, the voltage profile will differ from an hour to an hour or sometimes from second to second. Usually, one of the greatest attentions is the maximum load because it acts the peak voltage varies from source to the end of the radial line, particularly when the voltage source is minimum. Fig. 3-2 shows a simple line diagram of three phase, 60Hz, 120kV, which is connected to 120kV/25kV stepdown transformer to feed seven loads distributed along 60Km radial power grid. The parameters of radial line are ($R=0.1153\Omega/Km$, $X_L=0.5655\Omega/Km$). The FSCB is

installed at the end of line-2 (L2) as the optimum location. The maximum load capacity is 10.5 MVA and the load power factor is 0.9. The load is evenly distributed along the line. The prevalent FSCB is selected in this model, its capacity is $Q_{LC} = 20Kvar$, the voltage rated is , the current magnitude is $I_{LC} = 33.33A$, and the reactance value is $X_{LC} = 18 \Omega$. From the equations (2-21) – (2-29) calculated compensation capacity and the results are illustrated in the following values:

Fig. 3-2 Equivalent line diagram of radial distribution network with FSCB

Here, $X=7$, $Y=5$, the compensation capacity $Q_c = 3XYQ_{LC} = 2100Kvar$. Also, in this system the degree of compensation is $\gamma = 90\%$. The model has been examined during series and shunt compensation at the same capacity to compare and analyze the result with different load condition and power factor.

3.3.2 Simulation Results and Analysis with FSCB During Steady State Operation

In fig. 3-2, the radial distribution system has been studied during different load conditions and power factor in the following subsection:

3.3.2.1 Adaptability of Series Capacitor with a Long Radial Distribution Network During Various Load Conditions

The radial distribution system in fig. 3-2 has been investigated during different load conditions. The effect of series capacitor in radial distribution circuit carried out during maximum, base and light load condition. Table 3-2 and fig. 3-3 represent

the result during different load condition. From table 3-2 and fig. 3-3, it is noticed that the voltage drops in the radial power circuit increases when the load is high (the voltage drop during peak load is higher than the voltage drop during base and light load). Also, the reactive power is insufficient due to heavy load, and the voltage quality cannot meet the requirements of load. Therefore, the insertion of series capacitor in the radial power grid improves the voltage quality during different types of load condition and decreases the voltage deviation. In the worst cases, the maximum voltage deviation reduces from -13.67% to -3.1%, which occurs at bus-7 during peak load. In the peak load condition, the voltage at bus-3 reaches to 25.71kV after installation of series capacitor to the system, whereas the voltage reaches to 25.59kV and 25.53kV during base and light load respectively. After introducing series capacitor, standard value of voltage in the grid is achieved that is 25kV and voltage deviation found not greater than -3.1% (less than standard value i.e. ($\pm 7\%$) in extreme load. The series capacitor is self-regulated with the load, the effect of compensation increases when the load is heavy and decreases when the load is light, that can meet the voltage regulation requirements of the system. Moreover, the voltage deviation highly decreases during base and light load. The insertion of FSCB in the system minimizes the voltage deviation at bus-7 from -7.8% to -1.19% during base load and from -4.74% to -0.268% during light load. When the FSCB inserted to the system, it is noticed that the compensation point voltage (bus-3) is increased by 2.79kV, 1.71kV and 1.15kV in cases of peak, base and light load respectively. Also, from the results, it is noticed that the voltage in the extreme load increases by 2.63kV, 1.65kV and 1.12kV during maximum, base and light load respectively. It is concluded that the capacitance is proportional to the square of the current, and the voltage compensated by the series capacitor is proportional to the line current. Therefore, as the line capacity increases, the current increases and the compensated voltage increases. This is the load-adaptive property of series compensation, and it is also a feature that is not available in other reactive power compensation.

Fig. 3-3 The Voltage Profile During FSCB With Different Load Conditions

Table 3-2 Voltage quality with/without FSCB during different load conditions

Load Case Voltage Quality	Peak Load			Base Load			Light Load		
	V_{rms} (kV)		Voltage Increase kV	V_{rms} (kV)		Voltage Increase kV	V_{rms} (kV)		Voltage Increase kV
	without FSCB	With FSCB		without FSCB	With FSCB		without FSCB	With FSCB	
Bus-1	24.99	25.05	0.06	25.14	25.17	0.03	25.22	25.24	0.02
Bus-2	24.01	24.2	0.19	24.56	24.63	0.07	24.83	24.87	0.04
Bus-3	22.92	25.71	2.79	23.88	25.59	1.71	24.38	25.53	1.15
Bus-4	22.49	25.23	2.74	23.62	25.31	1.69	24.20	25.34	1.14
Bus-5	22.01	24.68	2.67	23.31	24.98	1.67	23.99	25.12	1.13
Bus-6	21.71	24.35	2.64	23.12	24.78	1.66	23.86	24.99	1.13
Bus-7	21.59	24.22	2.63	23.05	24.70	1.65	23.81	24.93	1.12

3.3.2.2 Adaptability of Series Capacitor with a Long Radial Distribution Network During Different Power Factor

The compensation effect of series capacitor is related to the power factor of the load because the voltage drop depends on two components PR/V and QX/V . In the network with higher power factor, the adjustment effect is limited. The series capacitor boosts the system in the worse condition. Sometimes the loads consume very high reactive power (low power factor); for example, the synchronous motor or a squirrel cage induction motor consumes high reactive power during starting operation higher than that power consumed during normal operation. The voltage drop during starting motor may be very high and inappropriate to other clients connected to the network. In the worst case, the high reactive power consumed during motor starting causes exaggerated voltage drops, which may make the motor unable to start (For more information see Ch-5). FSCB is inserted in the grid to solve aforementioned problem and boost the voltage quality.

The adaptability of series capacitor has been examined during different power factor values. Assuming the load power factor values are $\cos \theta = 0.9, 0.85 \text{ and } 0.8$; the analysis and the effect of series capacitor compensation have been investigated during various load power factor values at maximum load condition. Fig. 3-4 and Table 3-3 illustrate the improvement of voltage quality during different power factors values. From Fig. 3-4 and Table 3-3, it is observed that the FSCB improves the voltage profile. It is investigated that the voltage levels at bus-3 increase by 2.79kV, 3.30kV and 3.71kV when the power factor values are 0.9, 0.85 and 0.8 respectively (i.e., the voltage deviations percentage are +2.84%, +4.08% and +5.12% respectively). Also, it is noticed that the voltage values at the extreme load at bus-7 increase by 2.63kV, 3.07kV and 3.46kV when the power factor values are 0.9, 0.85 and 0.8 respectively (i.e., the voltage deviations percentage are -3.12%, -2.52% and -1.92% respectively). It is concluded that the voltage quality increases when the power factor reduces after installing the FSCB in the radial circuit, i.e., the series capacitor compensation is more effective when the power factor of the load is low.

Fig. 3-4 The Voltage Profile During FSCB With Different Power Factor

Table 3-3 The Voltage Quality with Different Power Factor

$\cos \phi$	0.9			0.85			0.8		
	V_{rms} (kV)		Voltage Increase kV	V_{rms} (kV)		Voltage Increase kV	V_{rms} (kV)		Voltage Increase kV
Voltage Quality	Without FSCB	With FSCB		Without FSCB	With FSCB		Without FSCB	With FSCB	
Bus-1	24.99	25.05	0.06	24.93	24.98	0.05	24.89	24.93	0.04
Bus-2	24.01	24.2	0.19	23.89	24.01	0.12	23.80	23.85	0.05
Bus-3	22.92	25.71	2.79	22.72	26.02	3.30	22.57	26.28	3.71
Bus-4	22.49	25.23	2.74	22.30	25.49	3.19	22.09	25.72	3.63
Bus-5	22.01	24.68	2.67	21.73	24.88	3.15	21.53	25.07	3.54
Bus-6	21.71	24.35	2.64	21.41	24.52	3.11	21.18	24.67	3.49
Bus-7	21.59	24.22	2.63	21.30	24.37	3.07	21.06	24.52	3.46

3.4 Shunt compensation (SHC)

Shunt capacitor (SHC) is compared with the previously studied Series compensation in the radial distribution system in this section. The system is investigated at various load conditions. Also, it is investigated with different power factor values:

3.4.1 SHC with Different Loads conditions

A SHC is installed at bus-7 in the radial distribution grid with the same capacity of the series compensation at the maximum load. The system is examined when the shunt capacitor is installed at extreme load at bus-7. From Fig. 3-5 and Table 3-4, it is observed that the shunt capacitor is not effective during maximum load condition. Also, it is noticed that the shunt compensation is more effective when the load is low and nice during base load conditions. The aforementioned characteristics are opposite with the case of series compensation where the compensation is more effective when the load is high and gently when the load is low. When the SHC is inserted in the system, it is noticed that the voltage at bus-3 is increased by 0.69kV, 0.82kV and 0.89kV in cases of peak, base and light loads respectively. In the peak load condition, it is investigated that increasing in voltage cannot meet the voltage standard. It is investigated that the voltage deviation values at buses 5 and 6 are 7.28% and 7.30% respectively and these values are more than the maximum voltage deviation standard of $\pm 7\%$. Also, it is noticed that the voltage in the extreme load increases by 1.7kV, 1.94kV and 2.08kV during maximum, base and light loads respectively. From the results in Table 3-4 and Fig. 3-5, it is investigated that the shunt capacitor is more effective when the load is low and gently compensated at base load condition but very badly compensated at peak load condition. All aforementioned characteristics are opposite with the case of series compensation where the compensation is more effective at peak load and gently when the load is light. It is concluded that, the shunt capacitor cannot adapt well with the different load conditions. It is possible to increase the capacity of the shunt compensation to meet the voltage standard at peak load, but this method creates a problem when the load is low (i.e., increasing the voltage at low load condition more than the standard voltage and causing some problems like increasing the risks of subsynchronous resonance phenomena).

Fig. 3-5 the voltage profile during SHC with different load conditions

Table 3-4 Voltage Quality With/Without SHC During Different Load Conditions

Load Case	Peak Load			Base Load			Light Load		
	V_{rms} (kV) Without SHC	V_{rms} (kV) With SHC	Voltage Increase kV	V_{rms} (kV) Without SHC	V_{rms} (kV) With SHC	Voltage Increase kV	V_{rms} (kV) Without SHC	V_{rms} (kV) With SHC	Voltage Increase kV
Bus-1	24.99	25.09	0.10	25.14	25.28	0.14	25.22	25.37	0.15
Bus-2	24.01	24.35	0.34	24.56	24.97	0.41	24.83	25.28	0.45
Bus-3	22.92	23.61	0.69	23.88	24.70	0.82	24.38	25.27	0.89
Bus-4	22.49	23.37	0.88	23.62	24.65	1.03	24.20	25.32	1.12
Bus-5	22.01	23.18	1.17	23.31	24.68	1.37	23.99	25.47	1.48
Bus-6	21.71	23.17	1.46	23.12	24.81	1.69	23.86	25.67	1.81
Bus-7	21.59	23.29	1.70	23.05	24.99	1.94	23.81	25.89	2.08

3.4.2 SHC During Different Power Factors

The SHC is inserted in the system at bus-7 with the same capacity as the FSCB. The system is examined during various power factor (0.9, 0.85 and 0.8) at the maximum load condition. Fig. 3-6 and Table 3-5 display the profile of the voltage quality during different power factors. It is observed that the effectiveness of the SHC decreases when the value of the power factor decreases. It is investigated that the voltage levels at bus-6 increase by 1.46kV, 1.44kV and 1.43kV when the power factor values are 0.9,0.85 and 0.8 respectively (i.e., the voltage deviations percentage are -7.32%, -8.6% and -9.6% respectively). It is investigated that the voltage deviation increases when the value of power factor decreases. It is concluded that, the shunt capacitor cannot adapt to various values of power factor. This characteristic is opposite with the case of a compensated system using series capacitor where the series capacitor is more effective when the power factor of the load is low. It means that the SHC is undesirable for customers because the starting of asynchronous/synchronous motors at the same time consume high reactive power (low power factor) and the SHC cannot meet the requirements of the load in this condition.

Fig. 3-6 The Voltage Profile During SHC With Different Power Factor Values (P.F)

Table 3-5 Voltage Quality With/Without SHC During Different Power Factor

Voltage Quality	0.9			0.85			0.8		
	V_{rms} (kV)			V_{rms} (kV)			V_{rms} (kV)		
	Without SHC	With SHC	Voltage Increase kV	Without SHC	With SHC	Voltage Increase kV	Without SHC	With SHC	Voltage Increase kV
Bus-1	24.99	25.09	0.10	24.93	25.04	0.11	24.89	25.01	0.12
Bus-2	24.01	24.35	0.34	23.89	24.24	0.35	23.80	24.15	0.35
Bus-3	22.92	23.61	0.69	22.72	23.40	0.68	22.57	23.25	0.68
Bus-4	22.49	23.37	0.88	22.30	23.12	0.82	22.09	22.94	0.85
Bus-5	22.01	23.18	1.17	21.73	22.89	1.25	21.53	22.67	1.14
Bus-6	21.71	23.17	1.46	21.41	22.85	1.44	21.18	22.61	1.43
Bus-7	21.59	23.29	1.70	21.30	22.96	1.66	21.06	22.71	1.65

3.5 Summary

From the simulation result and analysis, this paper discovered that series capacitor compensation has unique characteristics during its application in the radial power distribution network to improve the voltage quality. The paper analyzed, evaluated and compared the effect of the implementation of series and shunt capacitor compensation in the radial power distribution network during various load conditions and power factors with the help of basic theoretical theory and phasor diagram. The following comparative condition and the unique characteristics of series compensation have been detected:

- 1- The adaptability of series capacitor compensation during different load conditions has been simulated and studied. It is concluded that the series capacitor compensates more when the load is significant, and it compensates a little when the load is less. Also, it is found that the capacitance is proportional to the square of the current, and the voltage compensated by the series capacitor is proportional to the line current and the line current increases when the load increased. Therefore, as the line capacity increases, the current increases and the compensated voltage increases. This property is the load-adaptive property of series compensation, and it is also a feature that is not available in other reactive power compensation.
- 2- The adaptability of series capacitor compensation during different power factor has been studied. The series capacitor compensation has more obvious

adjustment effect on the load when the power factor of the load is low. The series capacitor boosts the system in the worse condition. Sometimes the loads consume very high reactive power (low power factor); for example, the synchronous motor or a squirrel cage induction motor consumes a high reactive power during starting operation higher than that consumed during normal operation. FSCB can also adapt to different power factor values.

- 3- From the comparison between the series and the shunt capacitor compensation, it is noticed that the shunt capacitor cannot adapt to various load conditions. It is concluded that high compensation occurs when the load is low, and the low compensation occurs during peak load condition. The rating of reactive power of series capacitor is much smaller than the rating of reactive power of the shunt capacitor for the same change in voltage. The series capacitor bank participates its reactive power to the system in ratio to the square of the current, which means that it participates the most when desired. The opposite is true for the shunt capacitor, which participates less when the load is maximum and associated with low voltage. It is investigated that; the shunt capacitor cannot adapt to different load conditions.
- 4- It is studied that; the shunt capacitor cannot adapt to varying power factor. This characteristic is opposite in the case of compensating the system by series capacitor where the series capacitor is more effective when the power factor of the load is low.

From the characteristics mentioned above, we can conclude that the SHC is undesirable for the customers because the starting of a large number of motors at the same time consume a high reactive power (low power factor) and the SHC cannot meet the requirements of load in this condition. Also, SHC can poorly compensate when the load is high because its capacity is proportional to the terminal voltage (i.e., it compensates low, and the voltage drop is high in this condition). It is concluded that there be a high compensation by the shunt capacitor during a light load condition. This condition is precisely the opposite of the required adjustment direction. The lower voltage happened in the system due to the more massive load, and it is the worse compensation effect of the parallel reactive power compensation device.

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CHAPTER 4 Protection Performance During Application of FSSC to 25kV Radial Power Distribution Network

4.1 Introduction

In the previous year, there have been essentially three substitutional techniques to protect FSCB from the severity of faults. These techniques are explained more in the first chapter. All their protective designs and structures have identified advantages and disadvantages. The traditional triggered gap designs were introduced more than 65 years ago [7]. Initially, the protection performance due to spark gap was determined by their naturalistic flashover level. The spark gap with the advancement of technology became self-triggered, resulting in more specific protective levels. The gap is installed in parallel with MOV and the spark occurs to bypass the MOV near to the protective level. The conventional gaps demand to a large space between the conductor to ensure the empty space are secure during the gap exposed to the environmental conditions such as ice, snow and the insects...etc. The spark gap can also put in more closed cabinet to avoid the environmental conditions [23]. In 1980, MOV scheme was introduced which has Outstanding fundamental performance [24],[60]. However, it can be very expensive in many practical applications due to increase the requirements of MOV units. In high fault current condition, it has to absorb a huge energy during faulty period and for this reason MOV scheme combined with spark-gap scheme in order to bypass the FSCB when the energy reaches to the threshold level. For aforementioned reasons, this thesis presents the Fast Switch Series Compensation (FSSC) using Fast Vacuum Circuit Breaker (FVCB) as a new alternative technique solution. Not only this, the new technique supplies the system many improvements during disturbance. Also, this new technique has an advantage in terms of more compact size of power equipment, high performance and less environmental hazard. In addition, the thesis presents the comparison between the results of new protective device (FSSC) and conventional protective device during various types of fault such as Ph-g, 2Ph-g, and 3Ph-g fault. Since long time, there has been utmost need of more airtight, effective, coherent and environmentally robust equipment. Therefore, an intelligent protection scheme reduces the number of MOV which in turn more economical, efficient and compact size of FSCB equipment. Throughout the aforementioned investigation, simulation has been carried out with help MATLAB/SIMULINK during different types of faulty conditions

4.2 Conventional Method

4.2.1 Main Structure

In this thesis, the analysis of fig. 4-1 have been carried out to compare the conventional method of protection with the new protection technique during different types of faulty condition. The main components of the scheme in fig. 4-1 are FSCB, MOV, Control system, Spark gap, damping circuit and bypass switch/circuit breaker. The MOV absorbs the energy as soon as the fault occur in power grid and as soon as the energy reaches the threshold level, it sends a signal to trigger the gap via control system technology to bypass the FSCB within 1ms.

Fig. 4-1 Single Line Diagram of A FSCB Protected Through A Triggered Gap

Due to aforesaid characteristics of this gap, it is possible to make the larger gap between the two electrodes as compared to the self-sparking gap, making the performance of the triggered gap much lower dependent on external condition such as weather. The gap in this design also isn't self-extinguishing and the current stays in the gap until a breaker/bypass switch closes or power system breakers cut off the fault.

4.2.2 Operation and Technical Principle

The main components of this scheme are illustrated in the following subsections:

- MOV

Voltage and current of MOV characteristics are determined by the manufacturer to protect the FSCB dielectrics. The rating of varistor's energy is selected to be sufficient for the maximum fault current to operate bypass switch/circuit breaker within required time [8,9,19,61]. In some situations, energy dissipated in MOV is lower especially in Ph-G fault so that the FSCB does not get bypass. In some situations, the fault duration is very long so the energy dissipated in MOV is very high which in turn sends a signal to bypass FSCB. The MOV requires a protective voltage level to protect FSCB from overvoltage is 2 times the nominal capacitor voltage according to (4-1), where $I_{protect.}$ is the capacitor current rated [21,60,62]. The nominal capacitor current in this scheme is 240A. At this value, the protective level of FSCB is 15.32kV.

$$V_{prot.} = 2\sqrt{2}I_{prot.} X_C \quad (4-1)$$

- Gap

The gap get spark as soon as it receives a signal by the control system when energy reaches to the maximum level in MOV and this fault is called an internal fault (the fault is occurred inside CB protected FSCB). The current transformer (CT) diagnosed the current within 1ms and send a signal to the close breaker. The spark in the gap cannot be occurred when the fault detected as an external fault (the fault occurred outside the series compensation distribution line get protected and removed by CB [21,62,63]. The gap is the space between carbon electrodes. It exposed to the external conditions which make the gap spark in normal operation such as weather, dirt and insects.

- Circuit Breaker/Bypass switch

When FSCB malfunctioned, the bypass switch gets close to allow the FSCB to be bypassed (in case of internal fault) and inserted as soon as the fault is cleared. In many situations, the bypass switch is incessantly conveying the current of FSCB [8,9, 19, 21,61-63]. However, in some situations, capital can be saved by utilizing bypass switch with a continuous current rating lower than that of the FSCB. This can be validated by the evidence that the maximum continuous current in the network is lower when the circuit breaker is in closed position (bypass).

- Control System

The equation (4-2) explains the dissipated energy in MOV. The energy sucking by MOV device measured through control system equipment and send a signal to the gap as soon as the energy reached the threshold level [8,21].

$$E = \int V_{mov} I_{mov} dt \quad (4-2)$$

- Damping Circuit

The damping equipment is a circuit having reactor connected in parallel with resistor. These components are substantial for limiting fault current [8,19,61,62]. The purpose of damping equipment is nullifying the discharge capacitor current and thus rapidly minimize the voltage across the closed bypass switch. The current limiting reactor inductance is chosen to determine the maximum discharge current and frequency to save these parameters within the gap abilities, fuses, bypass switch and capacitors.

4.3 Intelligent and Fast Switch Series Compensation (FSSC)

4.3.1 Eddy Current Principle to Drive FVCB

FVCB is a direct-acting fast permanent magnet vacuum circuit breaker [64-71]. The working principle is shown in Fig. 4-2. The circuit breaker driving mechanism mainly includes a closing / opening coil, an eddy current disc, a draw rod, and a closing / opening holding permanent magnet. During operation, the magnetic flux of the closing / opening coils induces a reverse magnetic field in the eddy current disc to form a repulsive force, which is directly transmitted to the moving contact of the circuit breaker through the coaxial pull rod to complete the closing / opening action [64-71]. The force transmission is direct, stable, and open. The device moves quickly and has a small-time dispersion. The energy storage capacitor is used to charge the closing / opening coil, and the driving strength is proportional to the capacitor's energy storage so that the circuit breaker has a very strong breaking ability. The type test of Xi'an High Voltage Apparatus Research Institute shows that the circuit breaker can be closed within 8ms and opened within 3ms with a dispersion of less than ± 0.2 ms; its maximum breaking current can reach up to 80kA and can continuous breaking operation 100 times under current [68]. The excellent breaking capacity of the fast vacuum circuit breaker is mainly based on the rapid identification of short-circuit current, zero-crossing detection and phase control technology. The short-circuit fault fast identification technology uses the current instantaneous value and the current change rate as criteria to realize the fast prediction of the effective value of the short-circuit current. The large-capacity intelligent high-speed switch measurement and control unit developed by the short-circuit fault rapid identification technology can predict the effective value of the short-circuit current and issue an action command within 0.3 to 0.4ms after the short-circuit fault occurs [68].

Fig. 4-2 The Structures of Fast Vacuum Circuit Breaker

4.3.2 Operation and Technical Principle

According to the characteristics of the FSSC, a FSSC is used instead of the conventional series compensation protection to control the spark gap and the bypass switch. The high-energy, high-pressure MOV group with high-voltage fuse replaces the conventional MOV module. As shown in Fig. 4-3, where FSCB is the fixed series capacitor bank; MOV is the zinc oxide component; Damping circuit is used to limit the fault current ; FVCB is the fast vacuum circuit breaker (bypass switch) ; CT is the current transformer to read the current value and immediately send a signal to relay to bypass FSCB during disturbance. The damping equipment is a circuit having reactor connected in parallel with resistor. These components are substantial for limiting fault current. The purpose of damping equipment is nullifying the discharge capacitor current and thus rapidly minimize the voltage across the closed bypass switch. The current limiting reactor inductance is chosen to determine the maximum discharge current and frequency. The MOV component is used to limit the voltage across the FSCB to prevent the capacitor from breaking down when the line is shorted. Bypass disconnect switches are not an important equipment of the distribution series capacitor bank but it is recommended to permit appropriate commissioning and rapid series capacitor isolation for maintenance without cutting off service on the grid. Compared with the conventional protective device, the scheme utilizes a fast vacuum circuit breaker combined with rapid identification technology to detect the short-circuit fault.

Fig. 4-3 Fast Switch Series Compensation Device (FSSC)

Fig. 4-4 Field Installation Diagram of Fast Switch Series Compensation Devices in Real Life (China)

When the line is short-circuited, the FSCB is quickly bypass within 8ms and automatically open within 3ms as soon as the fault current removed, which greatly shortens the working time of the MOV group. For aforementioned reasons, the capacity of energy significantly decreases lead to reducing the MOV units. Compared with the traditional protective device, the new technique is significantly smaller than conventional (more compact). Moreover, the cost is greatly reduced and the structure is simple and reliable.

4.4 Simulation Results for the Protection Performance of FSCB

The radial power distribution network in fig. 3-2 (CH3) have been examined in the steady state operation. In this chapter, the fault current is applied at the end of line-2 as in fig. 4-5 and the protection performance for FSCB is examined during various type of fault. Both conventional method and a new protective device (fast switch series capacitor) are examined to compare and evaluate the simulation result in the following subsection:

Fig. 4-5 FSCB Scheme On 25kV Radial Power Distribution Network

4.4.1 Conventional Method

The conventional protective device as shown in fig. 4-1 is inserted in the system represented by fig. 4-5. Simulation result and evaluation is presented to compare the results between the conventional method and the new protective device during different types of fault such as Ph-g, 2Ph-g and 3Ph-g faults and are explained in the following subsections:

4.4.1.1 Single-Phase to Ground Fault (Ph-g)

In fig. 4-6, a single-line to ground fault applied in the network system (Fig. 4-5) and simulated at $t=0.01667$ second. Usually, circuit breaker (CB2) is closed during steady state operation. Relay open the CB2 at bus-2 (B2) after five cycles at $t=0.08333$ second. The fault current is eliminated from the system after six cycle, i.e. at $t=0.1$ second. From fig. 4-6a, it is inspected that the voltage across the series capacitor goes up to the protective voltage level as soon as the fault happened in the system and remains at this value during faulty period and drops to around 12.5kV at the moment fault current removed from the system. In this model, the setting of MOV current is 1.8kA to detect the fault as an internal fault in the grid. Fig. 4-6b represents that the current value across MOV reaches to a value lower than the protection system setting i.e. 1.8kA so that the fault current is detected as an external fault and avert sparking to happen which in turn FSCB doesn't bypass as in fig. 4-6e. From fig. 4-6c, it is observed that the absorbed energy in MOV reach to 0.48MJ and remains constant at this value due to opening the CB2 at 0.08333 second. This absorbed energy i.e. 0.48MJ is less than the threshold energy level (0.7MJ). In this condition, the damping equipment does not operate after the CB2 is opened. From fig. 4-6d, it is noticed that the fault current value reaches to 1.3kA. The fault current downs to small value and transmission line with FSCB commences to discharge during fault path.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4-6 Ph-G Fault (a) Series Capacitor Voltage, (b) Current Of MOV, (c) The Dissipated Energy In MOV, (d) The Fault Current, (e) The Gap Current.

4.4.1.2 Two-Phase to Ground Fault (2Ph-g)

In fig. 4-7, a double-line to ground fault scheme applied in the network system (Fig. 4-5) and simulated at $t=0.01667$ second. Usually, Circuit breaker (CB2) is closed during steady state operation. Relay open the CB2 at bus-2 (B2) after five cycles at $t=0.08333$ second. The fault current is eliminated from the system after six cycle, i.e. at $t=0.1$ second. In case of double-line to ground fault, two cases exist which are shown in figure 12. From fig. 4-7a, it is inspected that the voltage across the series capacitor goes up to the protective voltage level as soon as the fault happened in the system and remains at this value during faulty period. It is also inspected that the voltage across the series capacitor in phase-B collapses to zero as soon as the gap gets sparking. Whereas, the value of voltage across series capacitor in phase-A drops to around 12.5kV at the moment fault current removed from the system. Fig. 4-7b illustrates the

current across FSCB and MOV in Phase A and B. It is observed that the current in phase-B is higher than the current in phase-A. First half cycle of current in both phases passes through MOV and the remaining half cycle passes through FSCB as illustrated in fig. 4-7c. It is observed from fig. 4-7c that the MOV current in Phase-B reaches to 1.85kA which is higher than the protection level (i.e., 1.8kA), hence the fault current is detected as an internal fault which in turn bypass FSCB, whereas the current across MOV in Phase-A reaches to 1.5kA which is less than the protection level so the fault current is detected as an external fault and the FSCB does not bypass. Therefore, comparing the current values across MOV in both Phases and from the theoretical equation (4-2), it is examined that the energy absorbs by MOV based on the current across MOV. From fig. 4-7d, it is examined that the energy absorbs by MOV in phase-A builds up to 0.6MJ so the spark doesn't occur in the gap as in fig. 4-7f because the relay open CB2 at $t=0.08333\text{sec}$ causes the dissipated energy to stay constant at 0.6MJ which is less than the threshold level (i.e., 0.7MJ) and the level of voltage across FSCB remains constant at the value 15.3kV until the CB2 get opened. However, the energy absorb by MOV in Phase-B grows to 0.7MJ as in fig. 4-7e, as soon as the control system equipment sends a signal to the gap, the spark in the gap is occurred as in fig 4-7f lead to bypass FSCB because the energy absorb by MOV reaches to the threshold level and the voltage of FSCB collapse to zero through the damping circuit. Further, it is noticed from fig. 4-7e that the fault current level reaches to 1.5kA in phase-A, whereas the fault current level reaches to 1.85kA in phase-B and goes up to 2kA at the moment sparking gap.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4-7 Ph-Ph-G Fault (a) Series Capacitor Voltage, (b) The Total Current Crosses SCB And MOV (c) The Current Of MOV, (d) The Dissipated Energy In MOV, (e) The Fault Current Iabc, (f) The Gap Currents.

4.4.1.3 Three-Phase to Ground Fault (3Ph-g)

In fig. 4-8, a three-line to ground fault scheme applied in the network system (Fig. 4-5) and simulated at $t=0.01667$ second. Usually, Circuit breaker (CB2) is closed during steady state operation. Relay open the CB2 at bus-2 (B2) after five cycles at

$t=0.08333$ second. The fault current is eliminated from the system after six cycle, i.e. at $t=0.1$ second. From fig. 4-8a, it is inspected that the voltage across the series capacitor goes up to the protective voltage level as soon as the fault happened in the system and remains at this value during faulty period. It is also inspected that the voltage across the series capacitor directly collapses to zero through the damping circuit as soon as the gap gets sparking. It is observed from fig. 4-8b that the current level across MOV in each phase is more than the protection system level i.e. 1.8kA. From fig. 4-8c, it is noticed that the absorbed energy in each phase reaches to the threshold level i.e. 0.7MJ and as soon as the fault current is detected as an internal fault, the control system equipment sends a signal to the gap, the gap gets spark and causes the FSCB to bypass as in fig. 4-8e. From fig. 4-8d, it is noticed that the fault current level reaches to 1.87kA due to 3Ph-g fault and goes up to 2kA at the moment sparking gap.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4-8 3Ph-G Fault (a) Series Capacitor Voltage, (b) Current Of MOV, (c) The Dissipated Energy In MOV, (d) The Fault Current, (e) The Gap Current

4.4.2 Fast Switch Series Compensation (FSSC)

The intelligent device, i.e., FSSC as shown in fig. 4-3, is inserted in the system represented by fig. 4-5. Simulation result and evaluation is presented during different types of fault such as Ph-g, 2Ph-g and 3Ph-g faults and are explained in the following subsections:

4.4.2.1 Single-Phase to Ground Fault (Ph-g)

In fig. 4-9, a single-line to ground fault scenario is created in the network system at the extreme of line-2 (Fig. 4-5) and simulated at $t=0.016667$ second. Usually, Circuit breaker (CB2) is closed during steady state operation. Relay open the CB2 at bus-2 (B2) after five cycles at $t=0.08333$ second. The fault current is eliminated from the system after six cycle, i.e., at $t=0.1$ second. The intelligent high-speed switch and control unit developed by the rapid identification technology of the short-circuit fault can predict the effective value of the short-circuit current and issue an action command within 0.3 to 0.4ms after the short-circuit fault occurred. Subsequently, the intelligent FVCB responds to the command and the FSCB quickly bypassed within 8ms (i.e., the FVCB closed at $t=0.024667$ sec to bypass FSCB). From fig. 4-9a, it is examined that the voltage across FSCB reaches to the protection level when the fault occurred and immediately collapses to zero during remaining faulty period as soon as the FSCB get bypassed by FVCB to avoid overvoltage severity. From fig. 4-9b, it is noticed that the

MOV protects the FSCB until the FVCB closed and the current across MOV becomes zero because the fault current changes its path to the damping circuit as soon as FSCB gets bypass. Also, it is observed from fig. 4-9c that the energy still dissipated through MOV during 8ms period and it reaches to 28kJ and stays constant at 28kJ after the FSCB get bypass by fast protective device. Fig. 4-9d shows that the fault current reaches to 1kA as soon as the FVCB closed and reduced to 0.96kA in remaining faulty duration. The line current returns to the normal value when the fault is eliminated from the system at $t=0.1$ sec and the current transformer (CT) sends a signal to the FVCB and it get opened automatically within 3ms to achieve the reinsertion of FSCB in the system. The FSCB units in phase-A and phase-B remain in the system to boost the stability.

Fig. 4-9 Ph-G Fault (a) Series Capacitor Voltage, (b) Current Of MOV, (c) The Dissipated Energy By MOV, (d) The Fault Current

4.4.2.2 Two-Phase to Ground Fault (2Ph-g)

In fig. 4-10, a double-line to ground fault scenario is created in the network system (Fig. 4-5) and simulated at $t=0.016667$ second. Usually, Circuit breaker (CB2) is closed during steady state operation. Relay open the CB2 at bus-2 (B2) after five cycles at $t=0.08333$ second. The fault current is eliminated from the system after six cycle, i.e., at $t=0.1$ second. The intelligent high-speed switch and control unit developed by the rapid identification technology of the short-circuit fault can predict the effective value of the short-circuit current and issue an action command within 0.3 to 0.4ms after the short-circuit fault occurred. Subsequently, the intelligent FVCB responds to the command and FSCB quickly bypassed within 8ms (i.e., the FVCB closed at $t=0.024667$ sec). Fig. 4-10a represents that the voltage across FSCB reaches to the protection level when the fault occurred and immediately collapses to zero during faulty period as soon as the FSCB get bypassed by FVCB to avoid overvoltage severity. From fig. 4-10b, it is inspected that the MOV in phase-A and phase-B protect the FSCB until the FVCB closed and the current across MOV becomes zero because the fault current changes its path to the damping circuit as soon as FSCB gets bypass. Also, from fig. 4-10c it is examined that the energy still dissipated through MOV during 8ms period and it reaches to 41.5kJ and 70kJ in phase-A and phase-B respectively. The energies stay constant at these value after the FSCB get bypassed by FVCB. It is observed from fig. 4-10d that the fault current level reaches to 1.7kA and 1.8kA in phase-A and phase-B respectively as soon as fast protective switch closed and immediately reduced to 1.35kA and 1.5kA in remaining faulty period. The fault current gets clear from the system at $t=0.1$ sec. The line current returns to the normal value when the fault is eliminated from the system and the current transformer (CT) sends a signal to the FVCB and it get opened automatically within 3ms to achieve the reinsertion of FSCB in the system. The FSCB units in phase-C remain in the system to boost the stability.

(a)

Fig. 4-10 2Ph-G Fault (a) Series Capacitor Voltage, (b) Current Of MOV, (c) The Dissipated Energy By MOV, (d) The Fault Current

4.4.2.3 Three-Phase to Ground Fault (3Ph-g)

In fig. 4-11, a three-line to ground fault scenario is created in the network system (Fig. 4-5.) and simulated at $t=0.016667$ second. Usually, Circuit breaker (CB2) is closed during steady state operation. Relay open the CB2 at bus+-2 (B2) after five cycles at $t=0.08333$ second. The fault current is eliminated from the system after six cycle, i.e., at $t=0.1$ second. The intelligent high-speed switch and control unit developed by the rapid identification technology of the short-circuit fault can predict the effective value of the short-circuit current and issue an action command within 0.3 to 0.4ms after the short-circuit fault occurred. Subsequently, the intelligent FVCB responds to the command and the FSCB quickly bypassed within 8ms (i.e., the FVCB closed at $t=0.024667$ sec to bypass FSCB). From fig. 4-11a, it is noticed that the voltage across FSCB reaches to the protection level after the fault occurred and immediately collapses to zero in remaining faulty period as soon as the FSCB bypassed by FVCB to avoid

overvoltage severity. It is noticed from fig. 4-11b that the MOV in each phase protects the FSCB until the FVCB closed and the current across MOV becomes zero because the fault current changes its path to the damping circuit as soon as FSCB bypassed. From fig. 4-11c, it is noticed that the energy still dissipated through MOV during 8ms period and it reaches to 59kJ, 70kJ and 24.5kJ in phase-A, phase-B, and phase-C respectively. The energy stays constant at these value after the FSCB bypassed by FVCB. It is inspected from fig. 4-11d that the fault current reaches to 2kA as soon as the intelligent breaker get closed (i.e., at $t=0.024667\text{sec}$) and it is quickly reduced to 1.57kA in remaining faulty period. The fault current is cleared from the system at $t=0.1\text{sec}$. The line current returns to the normal value when the fault is eliminated from the system and the current transformer (CT) sends a signal to the FVCB and it is opened automatically within 3ms to achieve the reinsertion of FSCB in the system.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4-11 3Ph-G Fault (a) Series Capacitor Voltage, (b) Current of MOV, (c) The Dissipated Energy By MOV, (d) The Fault Current

4.5 Discussion, Evaluation and Analysis of the Results

4.5.1 Results of The Protection Performance FSCB Using Conventional Method

The protection performance of FSCB using MOV and spark gap technique has been analyzed and evaluated during various types of fault with the help of MATLAB/SIMULINK. The result showed that this protection technique has ability to detect an external as well as an internal fault. In faulty case, different kinds of fault tested in the system such as Ph-g, 2Ph-g and 3Ph-g fault. The protection performance of FSCB has been achieved by MOV associated with suitable control system, spark gap, damping circuit and bypass switch. It is investigated that the FSCB in phase-A doesn't bypass from the system during Ph-g fault that's mean 0% FSCB bypass lead to stabilize the system due to two logical reasons. Firstly, the FSCB in phase-B and phase-C stays on the lines to maintain and enhance stability. Secondly, the device detects the fault as an external fault because the energy absorb by MOV does not reach to high level and hence threshold level. In 2Ph-g condition (Phase-A to Phase-B to Ground), the FSCB is only bypassed in phase-B, i.e. 33.333% bypass which is diagnosed as an internal fault because the energy absorb by MOV reaches to the threshold level. The FSCB in phase-B is not totally separated from the system but it is automatically reinserted in the system when the fault is removed. The FSCB in phase-A doesn't bypass from the system and the MOV is enough to overcome overvoltage severity because the system technique detects the fault as an external fault. The FSCB in phase-C stays in the system to boost the stability. The protection system operates immediately during 3Ph-g fault in order to bypass FSCB (100%) from the system to overcome the overvoltage risks across the FSCB and the fault current in this condition diagnosed as an internal fault. FSCB doesn't totally separated from the system but it does operate once the fault is removed. From all the previous conditions, the precise analysis and evaluation in this

protection technique is proved that protection performance of FSCB from overvoltage severity is very efficacious, robust and accurate.

4.5.2 Drawbacks of Protection Performance of FSCB Using Conventional Method

Besides the advantages of this conventional technique to protect FSCB as mentioned in previous section, there are some drawbacks in this technique that supposed to be further study to overcome. These drawbacks are described as follow:

Firstly: This technique required too many MOV units to absorb a huge energy during faulty conditions which in turn making the system uneconomical.

Secondly: The gap sometimes sparks in normal operations due to the gap exposed to the environmental conditions such as ice, snow, reptiles, etc.

Thirdly: The FSCB voltage reaches to the protection level voltage and remains in this value during faulty duration which may affect the dielectric of FSCB when the system exposed to the fault many times. This paper presents smart technique to overcome aforementioned drawbacks explained in next subsection.

4.6 Comparable Results Between the Protection Performance of FSCB Using FSSC and By Conventional Method

From the comparison of the results and analysis of two techniques, it is investigated that the protection performance of series capacitor using FSSC is more effective, economical and making the system more impact. The following points describe the comparison.

- 1- During Ph-g fault, it is observed that the dissipated energy reaches to 0.48MJ when the system protected by conventional method, whereas in case of FSSC technique, the dissipated energy reaches to 28kJ. Moreover, the MOV limits the voltage across FSCB up to the protection level during faulty period i.e. 15.32kV when the system protected by conventional method, whereas in case of FSSC technique the voltage across FSCB is immediately collapses to zero as soon as the FVCB bypassed the FSCB within 8ms lead to prevent the dielectric of FSCB from overvoltage risk which is far better than the protection by conventional method. Also, the fault current level in the first half cycle reaches to 0.95kA and 1.3kA in the remaining faulty period when the system protected by conventional method, whereas in case of FSSC technique, the fault current level reaches to 1kA as soon as the FVCB closed and reduced to 0.96kA in remaining faulty duration.

- 2- During 2Ph-g fault, when the system protected by conventional method, it is examined that the absorbed energies reaches to 0.6MJ in phase-A and 0.7MJ (threshold value) in phase-B lead to spark the gap in phase-B, whereas, in case of FSSC technique, the energy reaches to 41.5kJ and 70kJ in phase-A and phase-B respectively. Moreover, the MOV limits the voltage across FSCB up to the protection level i.e. 15.32kV during faulty period when the system protected by conventional method, whereas in case of FSSC, the voltage across FSCB is immediately collapses to zero as soon as the FVCB bypassed the FSCB within 8ms lead to prevent the dielectric of FSCB from overvoltage risk better than the protection by conventional method. Also, the fault current level reaches to 1.5kA and 1.85kA in phase-A and phase-B respectively when the system protected by conventional method and go up to 2kA during sparking gap. In case of FVCB, the fault current level reaches to 1.7kA and 1.8kA as soon as the FVCB closed and immediately reduced to 1.35kA and 1.5kA in phase-A and phase-B respectively during remaining faulty period.
- 3- During 3Ph-g fault, when the system protected by conventional method ,it is noticed that the dissipated energy reaches to threshold level, i.e. 0.7MJ and the gap gets spark in every phase when the system protected by conventional method, whereas in case of FSSC, the dissipated energies are highly reduced to 59kJ, 70kJ and 24.5kJ in phase-A, phase-B, and phase-C respectively. Moreover, the MOV limits the voltage across FSCB up to the protection level i.e. 15.32kV during faulty period when the system protected by conventional method. Whereas in case of FSSC, the voltage across FSCB is immediately breakdown to zero as soon as FVCB bypassed the FSCB within 8ms which in return prevent the dielectric of FSCB from overvoltage severity far better than the protection by conventional method. Also, the fault current level reaches to 1.87kA when the system protected by conventional method. Whereas, in case of FSSC the fault current level firstly, reaches to 2kA as soon as the FVCB closed (i.e. at $t= 0.024667\text{sec}$) and it is quickly reduced to 1.57kA during remaining faulty period.

4.7 Summary

In this Chapter, this thesis presented protection performance FSCB to 25kV radial power grid by an intelligent vacuum circuit breaker as a new technology and an alternative method to protect FSCB from overvoltage severity and reduced the fault current as well during faulty conditions. From the summary and comparable between the protection performance FSCB using an intelligent fast vacuum circuit

breaker and the conventional method, it is noticed that the following technical and economical improvements have been achieved:

- 1- The new protective device (FSSC) is more economical and compact because it reduced the dissipated energy through MOV, which in turn minimized the number of MOV components required for the operation.
- 2- In The protection performance with respect to overvoltage severity using FSSC technique is better than the conventional method because the voltage across FSCB collapses to zero as soon as the fast switch (FVCB) bypassed the FSCB. Whereas, the voltage across FSCB stays up to the protective level during faulty duration when the system protected by conventional method. For these reasons, the lifetime of FSCB dielectric with FSSC will be much longer than the lifetime of FSCB dielectric with conventional method.
- 3- It is investigated from the simulation result that the fault current level got minimize when the system protected by FSSC.
- 4- FSSC is free from the environmental impacts, it doesn't require to the gap which is exposed to the environmental conditions such as ice, insect and air pollutions which can cause spark in normal operation.
- 5- FSSC is easy to install in the system.

It is observed from all the previous technical and economical improvements, the protection performance of FSCB by FSSC is very efficacious, robust and accurate.

Chapter-5 Smart Design of Distribution Series Capacitor Bank Application for Improved Motor Start

5.1 Introduction

In this paper, the sub-synchronous oscillation phenomena of a synchronous motor fed from a series compensated feeder line is inspected. It describes precisely the considerations for the application of FSCB to radial power distribution grid. Starting of a large synchronous or asynchronous motor can induces a problem due to voltage reduction. Moreover, the sub-synchronous resonance phenomenon may occur when the load is light specially in the overcompensation condition [7],[19]. For aforementioned reason, this paper suggests a new technique to overcome this dilemma. It has been noticed that the voltage drops at the end feeder of radial line can be between 5-10 percent the rated level during the starting duration of synchronous motor load [72]. The most public process is the compensation of part of the feeder lines inductances and motors with either series or shunt compensation to provide the reactive power demand and improve the voltage regulation at the motor terminals. FSCB is adopted in the feeder lines to reduce the voltage drop caused by the inductive reactance of the line and the technique boosts a voltage rise which increases automatically and instantaneously with the demand of motor load. The ability of FSCB scheme to respond quickly with the variations of load better than the shunt compensation and can adapt with the various load condition. While series capacitor bank models have response times to the load variation, FSCB can also cause sub-synchronous resonance phenomenon when the motor start to operate or ferro-resonance phenomenon in transformers. In particular, it has long been noticed that when the feeder lines are compensated with series capacitors, the impedance of the feeder line and the impedance of motor can interact resulting in electrical sub-synchronous resonance oscillations either on motor starting or when the load is changed. This paper introduced a new technique to overcome this dilemma instead of conventional method and it is investigated in this chapter by means MATLAB/SIMULINK.

5.2 Self-Excitation During Starting Synchronous/Asynchronous Motors

A series resonance phenomenon occurs due to the incorporation of an inductance and a capacitor. For an electric power system, the frequency of oscillation of the resonant circuit is almost always sub synchronous, for instance from 10% to 90% of the fundamental frequency [7],[8],[19],[72]. For a circuit with an inductive load, say motor, for example, the reactance is a component in the equation that determines the total circuit inductance, and hence the resonant frequency of that circuit. The presence of a subsynchronous frequency has been renowned for creating problems during starting of large motors under specific situations which are called self-excitation. A more detailed analysis of this phenomenon is found in [8],[73],[74].

This problem most likely happens if the motor is large enough to cause a considerable voltage drop in the circuit reaches to greater than 10% during motor start and if the resistive load on the downstream side of the series capacitor bank is lower than 10% of the motor rating [7],[19]. Also, the following negative agents increase the self-excitation risks in the motors:

1. Increase the compensation degree more than 100%.
2. Low resistance value in the network lines
3. Increase the moment of inertia of the motor loads
4. Increase the mechanical moment of the motor loads
5. A low voltage level of the source.

5.3 Basic Concepts of Sub Synchronous Resonance (SSR)

Many components make up the power system, but they can be broadly classified into three categories: resistive components (such as resistors in transmission lines), inductive components (such as Motors, voltage transformers, line reactance), and capacitive components (series or shunt capacitors). The resistance in the system is constant, but the inductive reactance and capacitive reactance in the system are closely related to the system frequency. As the system frequency changes, the inductive reactance and capacitive reactance values also change, and the inductive components still exist. According to the magnetic saturation phenomenon, the inductive reactance value of the inductive component in the system is not only related to the system frequency but also related to the saturation of the core of the inductor component in the motor or transformer windings [8],[19],[38],[73],[74]. When the power system is in normal operation, the equivalent inductive reactance

and the equivalent capacitive reactance in the power grid are not equal, and no resonance phenomenon occurs in the network. When the system frequency changes, the inductive reactance and capacitive reactance of the whole system may be equal ($WL=1/WC$). Therefore, the resonance occurs in the system and appears in the entire network. At the same time, the resonance phenomenon is not easy to disappear by itself. The resonant overvoltage will not only occur when the circuit changes, but will continue to exist in the network for a long time after the external impact disappears [1],[19],[73],[74].

When the power system is in normal operation, the equivalent inductive reactance and the equivalent capacitive reactance in the power grid are not equal, and no resonance phenomenon occurs in the network. The system deviates from the original normal operation to another new state due to the system operation mode changes significantly (for example, when the load is light causing self-excitation in the motor or the system breaker is closed or malfunctions, etc.). At this time, the inductive reactance and capacitive reactance in the system change, and the parameter matching may occur causing the system to resonate and generate overvoltage. It is a serious threat faces up the safe operation of power components.

In general, resistive and capacitive components in a network can be approximated as linear components, and inductive components cannot be considered as linear parametric components due to magnetic saturation [7],[8],[73],[74]. Depending on the network structure and voltage level, the resonances may occur in the power system can generally be classified into the following three types:

- 1) Linear Resonance: Inductive components that cause this type of resonance are the same as resistors and capacitors, and can be regarded as linear components with fixed inductance values.
- 2) Subsynchronous resonance in the motor or a ferromagnetic resonance in transformer: These resonances are a nonlinear resonance. At this time, the inductance is no longer a constant level, but the voltage and current change. The equivalent inductance value constantly changes when the inductance and capacitance expose to the parameters match and causing resonance in the circuit.
- 3) Parameter resonance: When the network changes under the influence of the external impacts, the parameters of some inductive components in the network will change periodically. The parameter resonance may occur when the inductance and capacitance in the network match the parameters.

5.4 Treatment Method of Sub Synchronous Resonance (SSR)

In order to suppress the phenomenon of sub-synchronous resonance in the distribution line equipped with the series compensation device, the commonly used methods are:

- (1) When using series compensation technology to improve the voltage quality of radial distribution lines, use full compensation or under compensation as much as possible
- (2) When determining the installation location and capacity of the fixed series compensation device, the voltage level of each bus of the line after the location of series compensation device should be equal to or less than 107% ($\leq 107\%$) of the rated voltage of the line, that is the phenomenon of overvoltage after compensation is avoided.
- (3) The new technology method in this thesis can overcome the SSR problem automatically when the SSR problem occurs in the network.
- (4) Not all lines with series compensation capacitors will have SSR after the series capacitors are put into operation. The occurrence of sub synchronous resonance phenomenon has certain requirements on the resistance, reactance and saturation characteristics of the circuit [7],[8],[73],[74]. Therefore, before installing the series compensation device, it should be based on the specific line, the capacitance of the series capacitor, and the saturation characteristics of the motor in the system.

In order to make the whole line voltage meet the voltage quality requirements and have to adopt the over-compensation method, SSR can be avoided by resonance damping equipment.

5.5 Resonance Damping Equipment

5.5.1 Conventional Method

The investigators presented their effort to avoid SSR problem in the system, and they suggest some solutions, but there are some disadvantages in their suggestions [7], [8]. The most common are discussed below:

- i. Temporary Bypass of The Series Capacitor Bank During the Starting Sequence

This bypass is not an acceptable solution due to two reasons. The first reason is that the voltage drop is too high in most cases in the network due to the bypassed of the series capacitor. The second reason is that one of the goals of the series

capacitor is to enhance the motor operation and the motor unable to run with unacceptable efficiency due to an insufficient voltage quality during starting operation.

ii. Permanent Insertion of a Parallel Damping Resistor

The resonance problem can usually be eradicated by this method, but this solution also is not acceptable because the power losses increase due to a permanently connected resistance.

5.5.2 New Technology Method

This paper suggests another solution to avoid a resonance phenomenon, which is explained in the following points:

- Temporary Connection of a Parallel Damping Resistor

This suggestion can repress the resonance severity without any power losses in the system. Also, the motor can start to operate smoothly without any problem. However, this paper suggests the damping resistor associated with the circuit of the SSR detector to insert or un insert the resistor in the network. The value of the damping resistor should be guardedly selected to mitigate the SSR phenomenon. The selection of damping resistor value mainly depends on specific rules such as the network characteristics and the risk of SSR phenomenon. Many investigators recommend that the value of a damping resistor should be between the values $R_d = (5-10)X_C$.

- Circuit of SSR Detector

Using the temporal connection of a damping resistor in parallel with a series capacitor bank requires suitable equipment to detect the harmonic oscillation in the electric network. The equipment should be able to detect the SSR phenomenon immediately when it occurs in the system to insert the damping resistor and overcome the risk of SSR phenomenon.

In Fig. 1, the circuit of the SSR detector contains the choke coil L with saturation characteristics which controls the input of damping resistor to regulation compensation. When the system is in normal operation, the choke coil L is not saturated, the current flowing through the coil is negligible, and the damping resistor has not been inserted into the operation. When the system exposes to SSR phenomenon, a continuous overvoltage is generated across the series capacitor, and the coil is rapidly saturated. A coil with a high inductive value quickly changes to a coil with only a small inductive value, which will automatically insert the damping

resistor to the operation during SSR risk. That is, when the SSR occurs in the system, its circuit detector detects the resonance and automatically becomes active and insert the damping resistor.

Fig. 5-1 Smart Circuit of SSR Detector

The protection and control functions to detect SSR problem by electric circuit detector are illustrated in the following methods:

- 1- Subharmonic protection: This is the primary role of the circuit of resonance detector. The circuit of the resonance detector detects the subsynchronous resonance problem due to examination of the line current input in the circuit. The resonance circuit is not active during normal operation and the current across damping resistor equal to zero during the same operating condition. The series capacitor bank will stay in service during the damping operation permitting the series capacitor bank to improve voltage quality when the motor start to operate.
- 2- Fundamental frequency resonance protection: In overcompensation condition, the resonance at fundamental frequency may occur, and the output signal from this consequence is utilized to close the bypass breaker.
- 3- Current control: The risk of self-excitation in the motor when it starts to operate is augmented due to the low load current. The circuit of SSR detector is used to insert the damping resistor in parallel with the series capacitor until a lower load current pass. The damping resistor is connected in series with the circuit of resonance detector. Circuit of resonance detector detects the resonance phenomenon during light load when the motor start to operate, and it inserts the damping resistor automatically to the system to avoid subsynchronous resonance problem.
- 4- Support protection: This service will close the bypass breaker in case the damping resistor is unable to suppress the resonance problem or when the circuit of resonance is unable to diagnose the subsynchronous phenomenon.

- 5- Emergency breaker: This service will close the bypass breaker after a time delay in a state where the controlling of inserting the damping resistor unable respond to a signal from the sub-harmonic protection.
- 6- Automatic reinsertion: When the subharmonic fundamental frequency or self-excitation resonance juvenile has passed, the damping parallel resistor automatically disconnected from the system as soon as the circuit of resonance detector detects the eliminated resonance from the system

5.6 Proposed Model and simulation During Motor Start

Fig. 5-2 Model of Radial Distribution Network with Series Compensation During Motor Start

Table 5-1 Motor characteristics

Motor characteristics	Parameters Value
Power	1200hp
voltage	0.6kV
Speed	1800rpm
Friction factor	0.02056
Stator resistance, Rs	0.05588p.u.
Stator leakage reactance, L1	0.08p.u.
Field resistance	0.02124

In Fig. 5-2, the synchronous motor inserted to the system. The radial distribution network is examined during the initial operation of the motor. The motor characteristics are shown in Table 5-1. In Fig. 5-2, a synchronous motor

added at 24km from the source substation. It is started at $t=0.25$ second. The subsynchronous resonance has been examined when the motor start to operate during different load condition. The motor is associated with a soft-start apparatus, but for the target of this simulation study, the worst condition utilizing direct start operation has been taken in to account.

The motor has been examined and simulated in the following cases:

- Case-1

This case is purposely to induce the self-excitation phenomenon and compare the results before and after treatments by damping resistor. In this condition (case -1), the 1200hp synchronous motor begins operation with light parallel load and no damping resistor. In this condition, the simulation result of the synchronous motor self-excitation is clarified in Fig. 5-2. It is explained when the synchronous motor is energized at ($t=0.25$ sec). Fig. 5-3a and Fig. 5-3b demonstrates the motor current and speed respectively. From Fig. 5-3b, it is examined that, the synchronous motor speed unable to reach its standard operation value (the motor “locks in”) at speed equal to 13% of normal speed. Although the initial acceleration is almost normal.

Fig. 5-3 Motor Start/ Case-1(a) Stator Current (b) Rotor Speed

The signal of speed is very oscillatory after the breakdown of motor acceleration at 50% of the normal operation after that the motor speed reduced to an average value

lower than 0.18 per unit. From Fig. 5(a), we can observe that a low frequency oscillation that changes the waveform of fundamental frequency current. This low frequency oscillation period is around 0.23 seconds, or the oscillation has a frequency of around 12% of the fundamental frequency for a 60Hz system. This characteristic would not be uncommon for this kind of self-excitation case and that the starting current remains at a high level during the resonance phenomenon period. This condition mentioned above will cause the motor to procrastinate.

- Case-2

In the second simulation, the condition will specify the damping resistor value that will suppress the phenomenon of self-excitation motor with the same condition as case-1. A 106.2 Ω damping resistor is connected in series with the circuit of SSR detector, and both are connected in parallel with the series capacitor bank. From Fig. 5-4, it is investigated that, when the motor is started during a low parallel load, the circuit of the SSR detector detects the resonance phenomenon and immediately insert damping resistor (106.2 Ω) to avoid SSR problem.

Fig. 5-4 Motor Start/Case-2 (a) Stator Current (b) Rotor Speed

Therefore, the synchronous motor starting operation is carried out smoothly without any problem. It has also been confirmed that this value of the damping resistor removes the SSR phenomenon during starting motor with low load.

- Case-3

In the third case simulation studied defines that the synchronous motor is connected with parallel load adequate to avert sub-synchronous resonance phenomenon without the demand to insert a damping resistor in the system because the feeder current is sufficient to achieve this condition. When the current of feeder attains high levels, this value is utilized as a signal for the control system settings to disconnect the damping resistor automatically. From Fig. 5-5, it is noticed that for this condition, the parallel load is enough to suppress the SSR problem, and the parallel damping resistor is not demand. As in the prior condition, the motor speed level (Fig. 5-5b) reaches to its normal value and the starting current (fig. 5-5a) is decreased to its nominal level as soon as the starting sequence is accomplished.

Fig. 5-5 Motor Start /Case-3 (a) Stator Current (b) Rotor Speed

From the aforementioned dynamic simulation and study cases, it is observed that a damping resistor of 106.2Ω , which coincide to 5 times X_C (the series capacitor

bank impedance) is sufficient to avoid SSR phenomenon during motor starting in the case of low load condition. Also, the control system will separate the damping resistor when the feeder current reaches a sufficient level to avoid SSR. This condition will avert excessive power losses during the series capacitor operation.

5.7 Summary

The starting motors consume a high reactive power (low power factor) and the motor cannot start to operate during insufficient voltage quality. In this chapter, the paper suggested a new design to overcome the subsynchronous resonance phenomenon when the motor start to operate with different load condition. The new design is a damping resistor connected in series with a circuit of SSR detector, and both are connected in parallel with a series capacitor. It can detect the resonance phenomenon and automatically insert the damping resistor to the system. We can conclude that the new design can overcome the resonance risk when the motor start to operate smoothly. Also, it is concluded that the new design does not respond to inserting the damping resistor when the motor is connected with sufficient parallel load because the resonance does not occur in this condition and the parallel load is enough to overcome the resonance phenomenon. Therefore, the existence of parallel loads connected with the motor is desirable.

Chapter-6 Conclusions and Future Work

6.1 Conclusions

This thesis introduces new sophisticated techniques to improve the voltage quality in radial distribution system during steady state operation and disturbance as well. Many problems have been solved by new proposed methods. The thesis introduces the role of series compensation technology to improve the voltage quality and boost the transmission capacity during deliver the electric power by long radial distribution line in rural areas. In chapter-1, the thesis discussed the problems introduction, the main goals of this research, the background behind conducting this research, the literature review, the research benefits and the main causes of voltage quality problem. Also, it discussed previous studies and compared between the new techniques and the previous technologies. In chapter-2, the thesis proved the role of series capacitor to improve voltage quality by the main theoretical theories, phasor diagrams and how to select the optimum location of series capacitor. It proves by the main formulas that the series capacitor can adapt with various load condition and this feature is unavailable in shunt capacitor compensation. In chapter-3, From the simulation result and analysis, this thesis discovered that series capacitor compensation has unique characteristics during its application in the radial power distribution network to improve the voltage quality. The thesis analyzed, evaluated and compared the effect of the implementation of series and shunt capacitor compensation in the radial power distribution network during various load conditions and power factors with the help of basic theoretical theory and phasor diagram. The following comparative condition and the unique characteristics of series compensation have been detected:

- The adaptability of series capacitor compensation during different load conditions has been simulated and studied. It is concluded that the series capacitor compensates more when the load is significant, and it compensates a little when the load is less. Also, it is found that the capacitance is proportional to the square of the current, and the voltage compensated by the series capacitor is proportional to the line current and the line current increases when the load increased. Therefore, as the line capacity increases, the current increases and the compensated voltage increases. This property is the load-adaptive property of series compensation, and it is also a feature that is not available in other reactive power compensation.
- The adaptability of series capacitor compensation during different power factor has been studied. The series capacitor compensation has more obvious

adjustment effect on the load when the power factor of the load is low. The series capacitor boosts the system in the worse condition. Sometimes the loads consume very high reactive power (low power factor); for example, the synchronous motor or a squirrel cage induction motor consumes a high reactive power during starting operation higher than that consumed during normal operation. FSCB can also adapt to different power factor values.

- From the comparison between the series and the shunt capacitor compensation, it is noticed that the shunt capacitor cannot adapt to various load conditions. It is concluded that high compensation occurs when the load is low, and the low compensation occurs during peak load condition. The rating of reactive power of series capacitor is much smaller than the rating of reactive power of the shunt capacitor for the same change in voltage. The series capacitor bank participates its reactive power to the system in ratio to the square of the current, which means that it participates the most when desired. The opposite is true for the shunt capacitor, which participates less when the load is maximum and associated with low voltage. It is investigated that; the shunt capacitor cannot adapt to different load conditions.
- It is studied that; the shunt capacitor cannot adapt to varying power factor. This characteristic is opposite in the case of compensating the system by series capacitor where the series capacitor is more effective when the power factor of the load is low.

From the characteristics mentioned above, we can conclude that the SHC is undesirable for the customers because the starting of a large number of motors at the same time consume a high reactive power (low power factor) and the SHC cannot meet the requirements of load in this condition. Also, SHC can poorly compensate when the load is high because its capacity is proportional to the terminal voltage (i.e., it compensates low, and the voltage drop is high in this condition). It is concluded that there be a high compensation by the shunt capacitor during a light load condition. This condition is precisely the opposite of the required adjustment direction. The lower voltage happened in the system due to the more massive load, and it is the worse compensation effect of the parallel reactive power compensation device.

In chapter 4, This thesis presented protection performance of FSCB of 25kV radial power grid by an intelligent and fast breaker as a new and sophisticated technology and an alternative method to protect FSCB from overvoltage severity and minimize the fault current during faulty conditions. From the summary and comparison between the protection performance FSCB using the new protective

device (FSSC) and the conventional method, it is observed that the following technical and economical improvements have been achieved:

1. The new protective device (FSSC) is more economical and compact because it reduced the dissipated energy through MOV, which in turn minimized the number of MOV components required for the operation.
2. In The protection performance with respect to overvoltage severity using FSSC technique is better than the conventional method because the voltage across FSCB collapses to zero as soon as the fast switch (FVCB) bypassed the FSCB. Whereas, the voltage across FSCB stays up to the protective level during faulty duration when the system protected by conventional method. For these reasons, the lifetime of FSCB dielectric with FSSC will be much longer than the lifetime of FSCB dielectric with conventional method.
3. It is investigated from the simulation result that the fault current level got minimize when the system protected by FSSC.
4. FSSC is free from the environmental impacts, it doesn't require to the gap which is exposed to the environmental conditions such as ice, insect and air pollutions which can cause spark in normal operation.
5. FSSC is easy to install in the system.

It can be summarized from all the previous technical and economical improvements that the protection performance of FSCB by an intelligent vacuum circuit breaker is very efficacious, robust and accurate.

In Chapter-5, the thesis suggested a new design to overcome the subsynchronous resonance phenomenon when the motor start to operate with different load condition. The new design is a damping resistor connected in series with a circuit of SSR detector, and both are connected in parallel with a series capacitor. It can detect the resonance phenomenon and automatically insert the damping resistor to the system. We can conclude that the new design can overcome the resonance risk when the motor start to operate smoothly. Also, it is concluded that the new design does not respond to inserting the damping resistor when the motor is connected with sufficient parallel load because the resonance does not occur in this condition and the parallel load is enough to overcome the resonance phenomenon. Therefore, the existence of parallel loads connected with the motor is desirable.

It is concluded that the thesis investigated that the series capacitor compensation has forceful characteristics and some of those characteristics are not available in the other compensation techniques. The thesis also introduces new designs to overcome the voltage drop, overvoltage, and subsynchronous resonance problems. All the aforementioned problems have been solved and achieved by new suggested designs.

Not only this, the new suggested solutions improve the system technically and economically. Also, the new designs make the system very effective, robust and accurate.

6.2 Future Work

At present, the practical application of series compensation technology in the distribution network is relatively low compared with the transmission network. Few papers have been published in this topic is the main difficulties in this work. Further research on the fast-protective device and its application on series capacitor is required to improve the system technically and economically.

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Published Papers during Master Degree

A. Papers Have Been Published

1. Salah Abdulkreem Sofyan Mokred, Qin Lijun, Mazhar Ali, “Protection and Impact of Series Compensation Technology in High Voltage Transmission Line”; International Journal of Industrial Electronics and Electrical Engineering (IJIEEE), Jul, 2019, Volume-7, Issue-7, pp: 27-32
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B. Unpublished Papers (Under Review)

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